

```
In [1]:
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd

from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier, plot_tree
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
from sklearn.model_selection import cross_val_score
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.metrics import plot_confusion_matrix
from sklearn.metrics import classification_report
from sklearn.inspection import permutation_importance

from imblearn.over_sampling import SMOTE

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

import random
import time

pd.set_option('display.max_columns', 50)
pd.set_option('display.max_rows', 50)
pd.options.mode.chained_assignment = None
```

```
In [2]:
init_notebook = time.time()
```

1. Introduction

This notebook presents an implementation of two modules of the Data Driven Activity Scheduler (DDAS) as presented by Drchal, Certicky and Jakob (2019) (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2018.12.002> (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2018.12.002>)).

Input includes the Federal District Urban Mobility Survey (FDUMS) dataset, which contains socioeconomic features and activity diaries for the population in the Federal District, Brazil. (<https://doi.org/10.34740/kaggle/dsv/1315731> (<https://doi.org/10.34740/kaggle/dsv/1315731>))

2. Data Preparation

The first process in this project's pipeline is data preparation, which consists in importing the FDUMS dataset and performing some pre-processing such as data cleansing, re-labeling and feature selection. The goal is to end up with a dataset that is compatible with the input required by the DDAS framework. In the referenced paper (Drchal et al, 2019), it can be observed that the input dataset that was used is composed by three parts, which the authors call *soc*, *reach* and *counts*, in addition to the typical information of a travel diary.

2.1 Creating the *soc* dataset

First, the *soc* dataset is created. In order to do so, the available dataset must be analyzed and the features needed must be extracted. For this step, the tables *Person* and *Household* are used.

```
In [3]:
fdums_household = pd.read_csv('../input/urban-mobility-survey-federal-district-brazil/Household.csv', sep=';')
fdums_person = pd.read_csv('../input/urban-mobility-survey-federal-district-brazil/Person.csv', sep=';')
fdums_trip = pd.read_csv('../input/urban-mobility-survey-federal-district-brazil/Trip.csv', sep=';')
```

Taking a look into the columns of each imported table:

In [4]:

```
fdums_person.columns
```

Out[4]:

```
Index(['person_id', 'household_id', 'age', 'gender', 'education_level',  
      'area_of_occupation', 'has_driver_license', 'is_disabled',  
      'sector_if_private_worker', 'sector_if_civil_servant', 'expf_person'],  
      dtype='object')
```

In [5]:

```
fdums_household.columns
```

Out[5]:

```
Index(['household_id', 'people_in_household', 'bathrooms', 'bedrooms',  
      'vehicles', 'bicycles', 'motorcycles', 'dwelling_type', 'income',  
      'household_tenure', 'piped_water_supply', 'street_pavement',  
      'private_parking_space', 'year_of_newest_vehicle', 'domestic_worker',  
      'cable_tv', 'social_assistance', 'expf_household', 'macrozone',  
      'administrative_region'],  
      dtype='object')
```

In [6]:

```
fdums_trip.columns
```

Out[6]:

```
Index(['trip_id', 'household_id', 'person_id', 'tz_origin', 'tz_destination',  
      'ar_origin', 'ar_destination', 'mode_category', 'mode_type',  
      'activity_origin', 'activity_destination', 'activity_origin_companion',  
      'activity_destination_companion', 'trip_activity',  
      'trip_activity_category', 'trip_activity_consolidated',  
      'trip_activity_consolidated_category', 'origin_time',  
      'destination_time', 'trip_less_than_500m', 'trip_duration',  
      'includes_walk', 'includes_bicycle', 'includes_subway', 'includes_brt',  
      'includes_bus', 'includes_unlicensed_service',  
      'includes_private_charter', 'includes_school_bus',  
      'includes_car_as_driver', 'includes_car_as_passenger',  
      'includes_motorcycle_as_driver', 'includes_motorcycle_as_passenger',  
      'includes_taxi', 'includes_motorbicycle_taxi',  
      'includes_private_driver', 'includes_other_modes',  
      'includes_active_transportation', 'includes_individual_transportation',  
      'includes_collective_transportation', 'active_transport_walk',  
      'active_transport_bicycle', 'collective_public_transport',  
      'collective_private_transport', 'individual_private_transport',  
      'individual_public_transport', 'other_modes', 'expf_trip',  
      'expf_trip_adjusted'],  
      dtype='object')
```

The columns needed for the soc dataset must be extracted:

```
In [7]: soc_columns = ['person_id', 'household_id', 'age', 'gender', 'area_of_occupation', 'education_level', 'has_driver_license']
soc = fdums_person[soc_columns]

print('The number of rows in the soc dataframe is '
      + str(len(soc)))

soc.head()
```

The number of rows in the soc dataframe is 61358

Out[7]:

	person_id	household_id	age	gender	area_of_occupation	education_level	has_driver_license
0	1	3	60 to 69 years old	Male	Retired	Incomplete lower-secondary/middle school	Yes
1	2	3	50 to 59 years old	Female	Other	Incomplete lower-secondary/middle school	No
2	3	4	40 to 49 years old	Male	Self-employed (professional)	Incomplete lower-secondary/middle school	Yes
3	4	4	18 to 19 years old	Female	Student (regular courses)	Incomplete undergraduate school	Yes
4	5	4	10 to 14 years old	Male	Student (regular courses)	Incomplete lower-secondary/middle school	No

According to Drchal et al. (2019), in addition to the columns that were already extracted from the Person table, information about the each person's household, specifically the number of people living in the household and the number of vehicles available. We can derive this information from the Household table, with the columns "people_in_household" and "vehicles":

```
In [8]: import_columns = ['household_id', 'people_in_household', 'vehicles']
household_info = fdums_household[import_columns]
household_info.head()
```

Out[8]:

	household_id	people_in_household	vehicles
0	3	2	1
1	4	4	3
2	7	3	1
3	22	3	2
4	35	3	1

Now we merge this imported dataset to the soc dataset that we were developing

```
In [9]: soc = pd.merge(soc, household_info, on='household_id')
soc.head()
```

Out[9]:

	person_id	household_id	age	gender	area_of_occupation	education_level	has_driver_license	people_in_household	vehicles
0	1	3	60 to 69 years old	Male	Retired	Incomplete lower-secondary/middle school	Yes	2	1
1	2	3	50 to 59 years old	Female	Other	Incomplete lower-secondary/middle school	No	2	1
2	3	4	40 to 49 years old	Male	Self-employed (professional)	Incomplete lower-secondary/middle school	Yes	4	3
3	4	4	18 to 19 years old	Female	Student (regular courses)	Incomplete undergraduate school	Yes	4	3
4	5	4	10 to 14 years old	Male	Student (regular courses)	Incomplete lower-secondary/middle school	No	4	3

We have to create the *soc* dataset only for the individuals for which there is information in the Trips table (not all individuals in the People table are also covered by the Trips table)

```
In [10]: individuals = fdums_trip.person_id.unique()
soc = soc.loc[soc['person_id'].isin(individuals)]

print('The number of rows in the soc dataframe is '
      + str(len(soc)))

soc.head()
```

The number of rows in the *soc* dataframe is 44101

Out[10]:

	person_id	household_id	age	gender	area_of_occupation	education_level	has_driver_license	people_in_household	vehicles
0	1	3	60 to 69 years old	Male	Retired	Incomplete lower-secondary/middle school	Yes	2	1
1	2	3	50 to 59 years old	Female	Other	Incomplete lower-secondary/middle school	No	2	1
2	3	4	40 to 49 years old	Male	Self-employed (professional)	Incomplete lower-secondary/middle school	Yes	4	3
3	4	4	18 to 19 years old	Female	Student (regular courses)	Incomplete undergraduate school	Yes	4	3
4	5	4	10 to 14 years old	Male	Student (regular courses)	Incomplete lower-secondary/middle school	No	4	3

Now we know that our *soc* dataframe has 44,101 rows. Let's check how many of those have missing values:

```
In [11]: print('The number of rows in the soc dataframe with missing values is '
          + str(soc.shape[0] - soc.dropna().shape[0]))
```

The number of rows in the soc dataframe with missing values is 239

Since only a few rows (<1%) have missing values, we'd better just drop these rows.

```
In [12]: soc = soc.dropna()
          print('The number of rows in the soc dataframe is '
                + str(len(soc)))
```

The number of rows in the soc dataframe is 43862

For the DDAS framework, we will be using the Decision Tree Classifier model from the scikit-learn library. This model, however, does not accept categorical features as input. Therefore, we need to relabel all categorical values in our soc dataframe. We will start with the 'age' feature, which we will map into ordinal categories. Let's check what are the possible values, so we can map them:

```
In [13]: soc.age.unique()
```

```
Out[13]: array(['60 to 69 years old', '50 to 59 years old', '40 to 49 years old',
              '18 to 19 years old', '10 to 14 years old', '30 to 39 years old',
              '25 to 29 years old', '20 to 24 years old', '5 to 9 years old',
              '15 to 17 years old', 'More than 80 years old',
              '70 to 79 years old', '0 to 4 years old'], dtype=object)
```

```
In [14]:
map_age = {'0 to 4 years old': 1,
           '5 to 9 years old': 2,
           '10 to 14 years old': 3,
           '15 to 17 years old': 4,
           '18 to 19 years old': 5,
           '20 to 24 years old': 6,
           '25 to 29 years old': 7,
           '30 to 39 years old': 8,
           '40 to 49 years old': 9,
           '50 to 59 years old': 10,
           '60 to 69 years old': 11,
           '70 to 79 years old': 12,
           'More than 80 years old': 13}

soc.age = soc.age.map(map_age)

soc.rename(columns={'age': 'age_group'}, inplace=True)

soc.head()
```

Out[14]:

	person_id	household_id	age_group	gender	area_of_occupation	education_level	has_driver_license	people_in_household	vehicles
0	1	3	11	Male	Retired	Incomplete lower-secondary/middle school	Yes	2	1
1	2	3	10	Female	Other	Incomplete lower-secondary/middle school	No	2	1
2	3	4	9	Male	Self-employed (professional)	Incomplete lower-secondary/middle school	Yes	4	3
3	4	4	5	Female	Student (regular courses)	Incomplete undergraduate school	Yes	4	3
4	5	4	3	Male	Student (regular courses)	Incomplete lower-secondary/middle school	No	4	3

Note that we also changed the column name to avoid misunderstandings.

We must do the same thing with the 'education_level' column, mapping its values to ordinal integers

```
In [15]:
soc.education_level.unique()
```

Out[15]:

```
array(['Incomplete lower-secondary/middle school',
       'Incomplete undergraduate school',
       'Complete upper-secondary/high school',
       'Complete undergraduate school',
       'Complete lower-secondary/middle school',
       'Early childhood/kindergarden level',
       'Incomplete upper-secondary/high school',
       'Complete graduate school', 'Illiterate',
       'Literate, but with no education level',
       'Younger than 6 years old / not student'], dtype=object)
```

In [16]:

```
map_education = {'Younger than 6 years old / not student': 1,
                 'Illiterate': 1,
                 'Literate, but with no education level': 2,
                 'Early childhood/kindergarden level': 3,
                 'Incomplete lower-secondary/middle school': 4,
                 'Complete lower-secondary/middle school': 5,
                 'Incomplete upper-secondary/high school': 6,
                 'Complete upper-secondary/high school': 7,
                 'Incomplete undergraduate school': 8,
                 'Complete undergraduate school': 9,
                 'Complete graduate school': 10}

soc.education_level = soc.education_level.map(map_education)
soc.head()
```

Out[16]:

	person_id	household_id	age_group	gender	area_of_occupation	education_level	has_driver_license	people_in_household	vehicles
0	1	3	11	Male	Retired	4	Yes	2	1
1	2	3	10	Female	Other	4	No	2	1
2	3	4	9	Male	Self-employed (professional)	4	Yes	4	3
3	4	4	5	Female	Student (regular courses)	8	Yes	4	3
4	5	4	3	Male	Student (regular courses)	4	No	4	3

Now we have to transform the values in the columns 'gender' and 'has_driver_license' into binary values (0 or 1). At the same time, we will change the column name of 'gender' to 'is_female' to maintain consistency.

In [17]:

```
map_gender = {'Male':0,
              'Female':1}

map_has_driver_license = {'No':0,
                           'Yes':1}

soc.gender = soc.gender.map(map_gender)
soc.has_driver_license = soc.has_driver_license.map(map_has_driver_license)

soc.rename(columns={'gender':'is_female'}, inplace=True)

soc.head()
```

Out[17]:

	person_id	household_id	age_group	is_female	area_of_occupation	education_level	has_driver_license	people_in_household	vehicles
0	1	3	11	0	Retired	4	1	2	1
1	2	3	10	1	Other	4	0	2	1
2	3	4	9	0	Self-employed (professional)	4	1	4	3
3	4	4	5	1	Student (regular courses)	8	1	4	3
4	5	4	3	0	Student (regular courses)	4	0	4	3

We need to transform the column 'area_of_occupation' into a column that indicates whether the person is student. In order to do so, we will map all values that indicates that the person is a student into '1' and the other values into '0'. Finally, we change the name of the column.

```
In [18]: soc.area_of_occupation.unique()
```

```
Out[18]: array(['Retired', 'Other', 'Self-employed (professional)',  
      'Student (regular courses)', 'Homekeeper', 'Businessperson',  
      'Private worker', 'Civil servant', 'Unemployed', 'Domestic worker',  
      'No activity', 'Self-employed (casual)',  
      'Student (extension courses)', 'Volunteer work'], dtype=object)
```

```
In [19]: soc = soc.rename(columns={'area_of_occupation': 'is_student'})  
  
map_is_student = {'Retired': 0,  
                  'Other': 0,  
                  'Self-employed (professional)': 0,  
                  'Student (regular courses)': 1,  
                  'Homekeeper': 0,  
                  'Businessperson': 0,  
                  'Private worker': 0,  
                  'Civil servant': 0,  
                  'No activity': 0,  
                  'Unemployed': 0,  
                  'Domestic worker': 0,  
                  'Self-employed (casual)': 0,  
                  'Student (extension courses)': 1,  
                  'Volunteer work': 0}  
  
soc.is_student = soc.is_student.map(map_is_student)  
  
soc.head()
```

```
Out[19]:
```

	person_id	household_id	age_group	is_female	is_student	education_level	has_driver_license	people_in_household	vehicles
0	1	3	11	0	0	4	1	2	1
1	2	3	10	1	0	4	0	2	1
2	3	4	9	0	0	4	1	4	3
3	4	4	5	1	1	8	1	4	3
4	5	4	3	0	1	4	0	4	3

Finally, the column 'vehicles', which originally indicates the number of vehicles in the household, must be transformed to indicate instead whether there is a vehicle available (binary, 0 or 1).

```
In [20]: soc = soc.rename(columns={'vehicles': 'is_car_available'})

def map_is_car_available(row):
    if row.is_car_available >= 1:
        row.is_car_available = 1
    else:
        row.is_car_available = 0
    return row

soc = soc.apply(map_is_car_available, axis='columns')

soc.head()
```

Out[20]:

	person_id	household_id	age_group	is_female	is_student	education_level	has_driver_license	people_in_household	is_car_available
0	1	3	11	0	0	4	1	2	1
1	2	3	10	1	0	4	0	2	1
2	3	4	9	0	0	4	1	4	1
3	4	4	5	1	1	8	1	4	1
4	5	4	3	0	1	4	0	4	1

As we are interested in investigating people's behavior regarding mobility, it is important to exclude the children from the dataset, as we understand they do not make decisions about their mobility patterns, they simply follow their parents. Hence, we need to drop all rows that regard young people, being values 1, 2 and 3 of the column 'age_group'

```
In [21]: soc = soc.drop(soc[soc.age_group <= 3].index)
print('The number of rows in the soc dataframe is '+str(len(soc)))
```

The number of rows in the soc dataframe is 36582

We can see that after data cleansing, we kept only 36,582 individuals from the 61,358 on the original dataset.

2.1 Creating the *reach* dataset

In order to create the *reach* dataset, we have to determine the average time each person would take to go from their homes to the location where they perform their main activity of the day, at 8 AM of a typical weekday, for each transportation mode. The first thing we have to do, then, is extract from the Trip table relevant information for our analysis.

In [22]:

```
fdums_trip.columns
```

Out[22]:

```
Index(['trip_id', 'household_id', 'person_id', 'tz_origin', 'tz_destination',
      'ar_origin', 'ar_destination', 'mode_category', 'mode_type',
      'activity_origin', 'activity_destination', 'activity_origin_companion',
      'activity_destination_companion', 'trip_activity',
      'trip_activity_category', 'trip_activity_consolidated',
      'trip_activity_consolidated_category', 'origin_time',
      'destination_time', 'trip_less_than_500m', 'trip_duration',
      'includes_walk', 'includes_bicycle', 'includes_subway', 'includes_brt',
      'includes_bus', 'includes_unlicensed_service',
      'includes_private_charter', 'includes_school_bus',
      'includes_car_as_driver', 'includes_car_as_passenger',
      'includes_motorcycle_as_driver', 'includes_motorcycle_as_passenger',
      'includes_taxi', 'includes_motorbicycle_taxi',
      'includes_private_driver', 'includes_other_modes',
      'includes_active_transportation', 'includes_individual_transportation',
      'includes_collective_transportation', 'active_transport_walk',
      'active_transport_bicycle', 'collective_public_transport',
      'collective_private_transport', 'individual_private_transport',
      'individual_public_transport', 'other_modes', 'expf_trip',
      'expf_trip_adjusted'],
      dtype='object')
```

In [23]:

```
import_columns = ['person_id',
                  'trip_id',
                  'ar_origin',
                  'ar_destination',
                  'activity_origin',
                  'activity_destination',
                  'includes_walk',
                  'includes_bicycle',
                  'includes_subway',
                  'includes_brt',
                  'includes_bus',
                  'includes_unlicensed_service',
                  'includes_private_charter',
                  'includes_school_bus',
                  'includes_car_as_driver',
                  'includes_car_as_passenger',
                  'includes_motorcycle_as_driver',
                  'includes_motorcycle_as_passenger',
                  'includes_taxi',
                  'includes_motorbicycle_taxi',
                  'includes_private_driver',
                  'includes_other_modes']

trips = fdums_trip[import_columns]

print('The trips dataframe contains information about '
      + str(len(trips))
      + ' trips performed by '
      + str(len(trips.person_id.unique()))
      + ' people')

trips.head()
```

The trips dataframe contains information about 113398 trips performed by 44101 people

Out[23]:

	person_id	trip_id	ar_origin	ar_destination	activity_origin	activity_destination	includes_walk	includes_bicycle	includes_subway	includes_taxi
0	1	1	Taguatinga	Taguatinga	Home	Shop	0	0	0	0
1	1	2	Taguatinga	Taguatinga	Shop	Home	0	0	0	0
2	2	3	Taguatinga	Águas Claras	Home	Main workplace	0	0	0	0
3	2	4	Águas Claras	Taguatinga	Main workplace	Home	0	0	0	0
4	3	5	Taguatinga	Taguatinga	Home	Home	0	0	0	0

The first thing we need to do is delete rows that regard people that have at least one missing information. This means that even if only one trip of the person is missing data, we will remove all trips for that person from the dataset, because we won't be able to perform proper analysis.

In [24]:

```
person_missing_values = trips[pd.isnull(trips.activity_destination)].person_id
trips = trips.drop(trips[trips.person_id.isin(person_missing_values)].index)

print('The trips dataframe contains information about '
      + str(len(trips))
      + ' trips performed by '
      + str(len(trips.person_id.unique()))
      + ' people')

trips.head()
```

The trips dataframe contains information about 113382 trips performed by 44096 people

Out[24]:

	person_id	trip_id	ar_origin	ar_destination	activity_origin	activity_destination	includes_walk	includes_bicycle	includes_subway	includes_taxi
0	1	1	Taguatinga	Taguatinga	Home	Shop	0	0	0	0
1	1	2	Taguatinga	Taguatinga	Shop	Home	0	0	0	0
2	2	3	Taguatinga	Águas Claras	Home	Main workplace	0	0	0	0
3	2	4	Águas Claras	Taguatinga	Main workplace	Home	0	0	0	0
4	3	5	Taguatinga	Taguatinga	Home	Home	0	0	0	0

We also need to check if there are rows with incomplete diaries. In order to do so, we will look for people who only perform 1 trip

In [25]:

```
# Slow cell
incomplete_diaries = trips.copy()
incomplete_diaries = incomplete_diaries[incomplete_diaries.groupby('person_id').person_id.transform(len) == 1]

print('There are '
      + str(len(incomplete_diaries))
      + ' people with incomplete diaries within the trips dataset')

incomplete_diaries.head()
```

There are 1120 people with incomplete diaries within the trips dataset

Out[25]:

	person_id	trip_id	ar_origin	ar_destination	activity_origin	activity_destination	includes_walk	includes_bicycle	includes_subway	includes_taxi
33	27	34	Samambaia	Lago Sul	Home	Main workplace	0	0	1	0
112	63	113	Plano Piloto	Samambaia	Main workplace	Home	0	0	0	0
123	75	124	Taguatinga	Plano Piloto	Home	Main workplace	0	0	0	0
385	294	386	Samambaia	Samambaia	Leisure	Home	0	0	0	0
388	297	389	Samambaia	Samambaia	Home	Main workplace	0	0	0	0

As the number of people with incomplete diaries represent less than 3% of the total population surveyed, we decide to drop these rows

```
In [26]:
person_incomplete_diary = incomplete_diaries.person_id
trips = trips.drop(trips[trips.person_id.isin(person_incomplete_diary)].index)

print('The trips dataframe contains information about '
      + str(len(trips))
      + ' trips performed by '
      + str(len(trips.person_id.unique()))
      + ' people')
```

The trips dataframe contains information about 112262 trips performed by 42976 people

Now let's check the possible purposes of the trips in our dataset, that is the possible values for 'activities' performed on the destination.

```
In [27]:
trips.activity_destination.unique()
```

```
Out[27]:
array(['Shop', 'Home', 'Main workplace', 'Main study place',
      'Taking someone somewhere', 'Other', 'Eating out',
      'Secondary study place', 'Personal matters', 'Leisure',
      'Secondary workplace', 'Health', 'Business'], dtype=object)
```

We can observe that in the FDUMS dataset, there are many more categories for activity types than what is described for the DDAS framework: 'sleep', 'work', 'school', 'leisure', 'shop'. Then, we now must map the values in our dataset in order to match the ones in DDAS. We also create an 'other' type to comprise the categories that do not fit in the existing labels.

```
In [28]:
map_activity_type = {'Shop': 'shop',
                    'Home': 'sleep',
                    'Main workplace': 'work',
                    'Main study place': 'school',
                    'Taking someone somewhere': 'other',
                    'Other': 'other',
                    'Eating out': 'shop',
                    'Secondary study place': 'school',
                    'Personal matters': 'other',
                    'Leisure': 'leisure',
                    'Secondary workplace': 'work',
                    'Health': 'other',
                    'Business': 'work'}

trips.activity_origin = trips.activity_origin.map(map_activity_type)
trips.activity_destination = trips.activity_destination.map(map_activity_type)

trips.activity_origin.unique()
```

```
Out[28]:
array(['sleep', 'shop', 'work', 'school', 'other', 'leisure'],
      dtype=object)
```

Now we have to define which is the main activity each person performs. If the person works, "Work" is their main activity. If not, and if they study, "Study" is their main activity. In all other cases, "Other" is their main activity. If the person performs the same kind of activity in different places during the same day, we compute the one that happens first. Therefore, we create a function to compute that, by iterating over the *trips* dataset and returning the Administrative Region where the each person performs their main activity.

In [29]:

```
def compute_main_activ_places(input_trips):
    '''Returns a dictionary with the Administrative Region where
    each person performs their main activity.

    Keyword arguments:
    input_trips -- dataframe containing trip information
    '''
    trips = input_trips.copy()

    dict_activity = dict.fromkeys(trips.person_id.unique())
    dict_places = dict.fromkeys(trips.person_id.unique())

    for row in trips.to_numpy():
        person_id = row[0]
        activity = row[5]
        cur_main_activity = dict_activity[person_id]

        if activity == 'work':
            if cur_main_activity == 'work':
                pass
            else:
                dict_activity[person_id]='work'
                dict_places[person_id]=row[3]

        elif activity == 'school':
            if cur_main_activity == 'work':
                pass
            elif cur_main_activity == 'school':
                pass
            else:
                dict_activity[person_id]='school'
                dict_places[person_id]=row[3]

        else:
            if cur_main_activity == 'work':
                pass
            elif cur_main_activity == 'school':
                pass
            elif cur_main_activity == 'other':
                pass
            else:
                dict_activity[person_id]='other'
                dict_places[person_id]=row[3]

    return dict_places

main_places = compute_main_activ_places(trips)

# Displaying the first 5 entries of the dictionary:
dict(list(main_places.items())[0:5])
```

Out[29]:

```
{1: 'Taguatinga',
 2: 'Águas Claras',
 3: 'Taguatinga',
 4: 'Plano Piloto',
 5: 'Taguatinga'}
```

Using this result, which is a dictionary that indicates the Administrative Region where each person performs their main activity, we start creating the *reach* Dataframe

```
In [30]: reach = pd.DataFrame.from_dict(main_places, orient='index', columns=['main_actv_ar'])
reach.reset_index(inplace=True)
reach.rename(columns={'index':'person_id'}, inplace=True)
reach.head()
```

Out[30]:

	person_id	main_actv_ar
0	1	Taguatinga
1	2	Águas Claras
2	3	Taguatinga
3	4	Plano Piloto
4	5	Taguatinga

The next information we need regards the Administrative Region where the person lives. This may be obtained from the `fdums_household` dataframe. We now write a function to compute that.

```
In [31]: def compute_home_place(input_person, input_household):
'''Returns a dictionary with the Administrative Region where
each person lives.

Keyword arguments:
input_person -- dataframe with information about each person
input_household -- dataframe with information about each household
'''

person = input_person.copy()
household = input_household.copy()

dict_home_ar = dict.fromkeys(person.person_id.unique())
household.set_index('household_id', inplace=True)

for row in person.to_numpy():
    this_person = row[0]
    this_household = row[1]
    dict_home_ar[this_person] = household.loc[this_household, 'administrative_region']

return dict_home_ar

home_ar = compute_home_place(fdums_person, fdums_household)

# Displaying the first 5 entries of the dictionary:
dict(list(home_ar.items())[0:5])
```

Out[31]:

```
{1: 'Taguatinga',
 2: 'Taguatinga',
 3: 'Taguatinga',
 4: 'Taguatinga',
 5: 'Taguatinga'}
```

We use the dictionary that was obtained from the previous function to create a new column in the `reach` dataframe

```
In [32]: reach['home_ar'] = reach['person_id'].map(home_ar)
reach = reach[['person_id', 'home_ar', 'main_actv_ar']]
reach.head()
```

Out[32]:

	person_id	home_ar	main_actv_ar
0	1	Taguatinga	Taguatinga
1	2	Taguatinga	Águas Claras
2	3	Taguatinga	Taguatinga
3	4	Taguatinga	Plano Piloto
4	5	Taguatinga	Taguatinga

In order to compute the average duration of the trip between the pairs of administrative regions in Federal District (*Distance Matrix* tables), we used information retrieved from the Google Maps API. The detailed procedure is described in <https://github.com/danielefm/DistanceMatrix> (<https://github.com/danielefm/DistanceMatrix>).

In the Distance Matrices we are using as input, the first column represents the administrative region of origin and each possible destination is represented in each of the following columns. In the cell where origin and destination cross, we get the value for the average time of travel between these two locations on a common weekday, at 8 AM.

```
In [33]: bike_distance_matrix = pd.read_csv('../input/distance-matrix-distrito-federal/reach_bicycling.csv', sep=';')
)

# Displaying the first five rows and columns
bike_distance_matrix.iloc[:5, :5]
```

Out[33]:

	Unnamed: 0	Abadiânia	Água Fria de Goiás	Águas Claras	Águas Claras Vertical
0	Águas Claras	22132.33333	29042.00000	1202.000000	1655.333333
1	Águas Claras Vertical	24872.66667	29757.33333	1364.333333	718.333333
2	Brazlândia	26495.33333	30625.33333	7448.000000	9023.333333
3	Candangolândia	23969.33333	28766.66667	2262.333333	2709.000000
4	Ceilândia	24848.33333	33125.66667	4213.333333	6016.333333

We need to rename the first column and turn it into the index for the dataframe.

In [34]:

```
bike_distance_matrix.rename(columns={'Unnamed: 0':'origin'}, inplace=True)
bike_distance_matrix.set_index('origin', inplace=True)

print('This Distance Matrix has '
      + str(len(bike_distance_matrix))
      + ' rows (possible origins) and '
      + str(len(bike_distance_matrix.columns))
      + ' columns (possible destinations)')

# Displaying the first five rows and columns
bike_distance_matrix.iloc[:5, :5]
```

This Distance Matrix has 32 rows (possible origins) and 53 columns (possible destinations)

Out[34]:

	Abadiânia	Água Fria de Goiás	Águas Claras	Águas Claras Vertical	Águas Lindas de Goiás
origin					
Águas Claras	22132.33333	29042.00000	1202.000000	1655.333333	8130.333333
Águas Claras Vertical	24872.66667	29757.33333	1364.333333	718.333333	7571.000000
Brazlândia	26495.33333	30625.33333	7448.000000	9023.333333	7467.666667
Candangolândia	23969.33333	28766.66667	2262.333333	2709.000000	11783.666670
Ceilândia	24848.33333	33125.66667	4213.333333	6016.333333	5223.666667

Then we do the same for the other Distance Matrices

In [35]:

```
car_distance_matrix = pd.read_csv('../input/distance-matrix-distrito-federal/reach_driving.csv', sep=';')
car_distance_matrix.rename(columns={'Unnamed: 0':'origin'}, inplace=True)
car_distance_matrix.set_index('origin', inplace=True)

transit_distance_matrix = pd.read_csv('../input/distance-matrix-distrito-federal/reach_transit.csv', sep=';')
transit_distance_matrix.rename(columns={'Unnamed: 0':'origin'}, inplace=True)
transit_distance_matrix.set_index('origin', inplace=True)

walk_distance_matrix = pd.read_csv('../input/distance-matrix-distrito-federal/reach_walking.csv', sep=';')
walk_distance_matrix.rename(columns={'Unnamed: 0':'origin'}, inplace=True)
walk_distance_matrix.set_index('origin', inplace=True)
```

We must now create columns in the *reach* dataframe to present the *reach* values from the Distance Matrices for each transportation mode, for each person.

In [36]:

```
def reach_from_distance_matrix(input_person, input_distance_matrix):
    '''Returns a dictionary with reach information (average trip duration
    between the person's Administrative Region (AR) and the AR where
    he/she performs their main activity, for a given mode).

    Keyword arguments:
    input_person -- dataframe with information about the person
    input_distance_matrix -- dataframe with the distance matrix for a given mode
    '''

    person = input_person.copy()
    distance_matrix = input_distance_matrix.copy()

    dict_reach = dict.fromkeys(person.person_id.unique())

    for row in person.to_numpy():
        this_person = row[0]
        origin = row[1]
        destination = row[2]

        try:
            dict_reach[this_person] = distance_matrix.loc[origin, destination]
        except:
            dict_reach[this_person] = -1

    return dict_reach

bike_reach_dict = reach_from_distance_matrix(reach, bike_distance_matrix)

# Displaying the first 5 entries of the dictionary:
dict(list(bike_reach_dict.items())[0:5])
```

Out[36]:

```
{1: 1502.0, 2: 1869.3333329999998, 3: 1502.0, 4: 4446.333333, 5: 1502.0}
```

And then for the other Distance Matrices:

In [37]:

```
car_reach_dict = reach_from_distance_matrix(reach, car_distance_matrix)
transit_reach_dict = reach_from_distance_matrix(reach, transit_distance_matrix)
walk_reach_dict = reach_from_distance_matrix(reach, walk_distance_matrix)
```

And finally we append those *reach* columns into the *reach* dataframe

In [38]:

```
reach['reach_bike'] = reach['person_id'].map(bike_reach_dict)
reach['reach_car'] = reach['person_id'].map(car_reach_dict)
reach['reach_transit'] = reach['person_id'].map(transit_reach_dict)
reach['reach_walk'] = reach['person_id'].map(walk_reach_dict)
reach.head()
```

Out[38]:

	person_id	home_ar	main_actv_ar	reach_bike	reach_car	reach_transit	reach_walk
0	1	Taguatinga	Taguatinga	1502.000000	1043.000000	3002.5	6139.0
1	2	Taguatinga	Águas Claras	1869.333333	1844.333333	4834.0	8212.0
2	3	Taguatinga	Taguatinga	1502.000000	1043.000000	3002.5	6139.0
3	4	Taguatinga	Plano Piloto	4446.333333	2281.666667	-1.0	19298.0
4	5	Taguatinga	Taguatinga	1502.000000	1043.000000	3002.5	6139.0

The *home_ar* and the *main_actv_ar* are actually not needed for the model, they were only auxiliary on the process of obtaining the *reach* columns. Hence, now we drop them.

In [39]:

```
reach = reach.drop(['home_ar', 'main_actv_ar'], axis=1)
reach.head()
```

Out[39]:

	person_id	reach_bike	reach_car	reach_transit	reach_walk
0	1	1502.000000	1043.000000	3002.5	6139.0
1	2	1869.333333	1844.333333	4834.0	8212.0
2	3	1502.000000	1043.000000	3002.5	6139.0
3	4	4446.333333	2281.666667	-1.0	19298.0
4	5	1502.000000	1043.000000	3002.5	6139.0

Finally, we create a unique table by merging the *soc* and *reach* dataframes

In [40]:

```
soc_and_reach = pd.merge(soc, reach, on='person_id')
soc_and_reach.head()
```

Out[40]:

	person_id	household_id	age_group	is_female	is_student	education_level	has_driver_license	people_in_household	is_car_available	reach_bike	reach_car	reach_transit	reach_walk
0	1	3	11	0	0	4	1	2	1	1502.000000	1043.000000	3002.5	6139.0
1	2	3	10	1	0	4	0	2	1	1869.333333	1844.333333	4834.0	8212.0
2	3	4	9	0	0	4	1	4	1	1502.000000	1043.000000	3002.5	6139.0
3	4	4	5	1	1	8	1	4	1	4446.333333	2281.666667	-1.0	19298.0
4	6	4	8	1	0	7	1	4	1	1502.000000	1043.000000	3002.5	6139.0

2.3 Organizing the *trips* dataframe

First, let's check how our *trips* dataframe is right now

```
In [41]: trips.head()
```

Out[41]:

	person_id	trip_id	ar_origin	ar_destination	activity_origin	activity_destination	includes_walk	includes_bicycle	includes_subway	includes_brt
0	1	1	Taguatinga	Taguatinga	sleep	shop	0	0	0	0
1	1	2	Taguatinga	Taguatinga	shop	sleep	0	0	0	0
2	2	3	Taguatinga	Águas Claras	sleep	work	0	0	0	0
3	2	4	Águas Claras	Taguatinga	work	sleep	0	0	0	0
4	3	5	Taguatinga	Taguatinga	sleep	sleep	0	0	0	0

```
In [42]: trips.columns
```

Out[42]:

```
Index(['person_id', 'trip_id', 'ar_origin', 'ar_destination',  
      'activity_origin', 'activity_destination', 'includes_walk',  
      'includes_bicycle', 'includes_subway', 'includes_brt', 'includes_bus',  
      'includes_unlicensed_service', 'includes_private_charter',  
      'includes_school_bus', 'includes_car_as_driver',  
      'includes_car_as_passenger', 'includes_motorcycle_as_driver',  
      'includes_motorcycle_as_passenger', 'includes_taxi',  
      'includes_motorbicycle_taxi', 'includes_private_driver',  
      'includes_other_modes'],  
      dtype='object')
```

The *trips* dataframe that we currently have is still not compatible to what we need to implement DDAS. We start the data cleansing process by dropping the columns that we won't need

```
In [43]: trips.drop(columns=['ar_origin', 'ar_destination'], inplace=True)
```

On the original study, only four types of transport modes were considered: *bike*, *car*, *pt* (transit) and *walk*. So, our first task for organizing this dataframe is to map the transport modes we have on *trips* into the categories considered in DDAS.

In [44]:

```
# Slow cell
def create_pt_column(row):
    if (row.includes_subway==1 or row.includes_brt==1 or row.includes_bus==1):
        row.includes_pt = 1
    else:
        row.includes_pt = 0

    return row

# Create a new empty column in the trips dataframe
trips['includes_pt'] = ''

# Check if any subtype of the public transportation mode is included in the trip
# for each row
trips = trips.apply(create_pt_column, axis='columns')

# Drop the subtype columns
trips.drop(columns=['includes_subway', 'includes_brt', 'includes_bus'],
            inplace=True)

trips.head()
```

Out[44]:

	person_id	trip_id	activity_origin	activity_destination	includes_walk	includes_bicycle	includes_licensed_service	includes_private_charter
0	1	1	sleep	shop	0	0	0	0
1	1	2	shop	sleep	0	0	0	0
2	2	3	sleep	work	0	0	0	0
3	2	4	work	sleep	0	0	0	0
4	3	5	sleep	sleep	0	0	0	0

In [45]:

```
# Slow cell
def create_car_column(row):
    if (row.includes_car_as_passenger==1 or row.includes_car_as_driver==1):
        row.includes_car = 1
    else:
        row.includes_car = 0

    return row

# Create a new empty column in the trips dataframe
trips['includes_car'] = ''

# Check if any subtype of the car mode is included in the trip
# for each row
trips = trips.apply(create_car_column, axis='columns')

# Drop the subtype columns
trips.drop(columns=['includes_car_as_passenger', 'includes_car_as_driver'],
           inplace=True)

trips.head()
```

Out[45]:

	person_id	trip_id	activity_origin	activity_destination	includes_walk	includes_bicycle	includes_licensed_service	includes_private_charter
0	1	1	sleep	shop	0	0	0	0
1	1	2	shop	sleep	0	0	0	0
2	2	3	sleep	work	0	0	0	0
3	2	4	work	sleep	0	0	0	0
4	3	5	sleep	sleep	0	0	0	0

In [46]:

```
# Slow cell
def create_other_column(row):
    if (row.includes_unlicensed_service==1 or
        row.includes_private_charter==1 or
        row.includes_school_bus==1 or
        row.includes_motorcycle_as_driver==1 or
        row.includes_motorcycle_as_passenger==1 or
        row.includes_taxi==1 or
        row.includes_motorbicycle_taxi==1 or
        row.includes_private_driver==1 or
        row.includes_other_modes==1):
        row.includes_other_modes = 1
    else:
        row.includes_other_modes = 0

    return row

# Check if any subtype of other modes is included in the trip
# for each row
trips = trips.apply(create_other_column, axis='columns')

# Drop the subtype columns
trips.drop(columns=['includes_unlicensed_service',
                   'includes_private_charter',
                   'includes_school_bus',
                   'includes_motorcycle_as_driver',
                   'includes_motorcycle_as_passenger',
                   'includes_taxi',
                   'includes_motorbicycle_taxi',
                   'includes_private_driver'], inplace=True)

trips.head()
```

Out[46]:

	person_id	trip_id	activity_origin	activity_destination	includes_walk	includes_bicycle	includes_other_modes	includes_pt	includes_car
0	1	1	sleep	shop	0	0	0	0	1
1	1	2	shop	sleep	0	0	0	0	1
2	2	3	sleep	work	0	0	0	1	0
3	2	4	work	sleep	0	0	0	1	0
4	3	5	sleep	sleep	0	0	1	0	0

Now we have to create a Y column for when our DDAS implementation predicts the transportation mode. This would be the reverse process of One-Hot-Encoding, because we would have to check which transportation mode column has the value of 1 for each trip and get the respective transport mode. However, some people might have more than one transport mode for the same trip. Let's check how many of these occurrences we find in this dataframe.

```
In [47]:
print('The trips dataframe contains information about '
      + str(len(trips))
      + ' trips performed by '
      + str(len(trips.person_id.unique()))
      + ' people')

trips.columns
```

The trips dataframe contains information about 112262 trips performed by 42976 people

```
Out[47]:
Index(['person_id', 'trip_id', 'activity_origin', 'activity_destination',
       'includes_walk', 'includes_bicycle', 'includes_other_modes',
       'includes_pt', 'includes_car'],
      dtype='object')
```

```
In [48]:
transfer_trips = trips.loc[trips.loc[:,['includes_walk',
                                       'includes_bicycle',
                                       'includes_other_modes',
                                       'includes_pt',
                                       'includes_car']].sum(axis=1)>1]

print('In the trips dataframe, '
      + str(len(transfer_trips.person_id.unique()))
      + ' use more than one transport mode on the same trip')
```

In the trips dataframe, 422 use more than one transport mode on the same trip

Since there are only 422 individuals that use more than 1 transport mode type in the same trip, it is easier to just drop those rows.

```
In [49]:
trips = trips.loc[~trips['person_id'].isin(transfer_trips.person_id)]

print('The trips dataframe contains information about '
      + str(len(trips))
      + ' trips performed by '
      + str(len(trips.person_id.unique()))
      + ' people')

trips.head()
```

The trips dataframe contains information about 111191 trips performed by 42554 people

Out[49]:

	person_id	trip_id	activity_origin	activity_destination	includes_walk	includes_bicycle	includes_other_modes	includes_pt	includes_car
0	1	1	sleep	shop	0	0	0	0	1
1	1	2	shop	sleep	0	0	0	0	1
2	2	3	sleep	work	0	0	0	1	0
3	2	4	work	sleep	0	0	0	1	0
4	3	5	sleep	sleep	0	0	1	0	0

Now it is possible to create the Y column for the MCM model, which we will call "mode"

In [50]:

```
# Slow cell
def create_mode_column(row):
    if (row.includes_car == 1):
        row.mode_type = 'car'
    elif (row.includes_pt == 1):
        row.mode_type = 'pt'
    elif (row.includes_bicycle) == 1:
        row.mode_type = 'bike'
    elif (row.includes_other_modes) == 1:
        row.mode_type = 'other_mode'
    else:
        row.mode_type = 'walk'

    return row

# Create a new empty column in the trips dataframe
trips['mode_type'] = ''

# Check which of the mode columns has the value of 1 and
# get the name of that mode
trips = trips.apply(create_mode_column, axis='columns')

# Drop the subtype columns
trips.drop(columns=['includes_walk',
                   'includes_bicycle',
                   'includes_other_modes',
                   'includes_pt',
                   'includes_car'], inplace=True)

trips.head()
```

Out[50]:

	person_id	trip_id	activity_origin	activity_destination	mode_type
0	1	1	sleep	shop	car
1	1	2	shop	sleep	car
2	2	3	sleep	work	pt
3	2	4	work	sleep	pt
4	3	5	sleep	sleep	other_mode

In order to properly train the Decision Tree Classifier in the future, we have to set the value for the last destination for each person as 'none'.

In [51]:

```
def set_last_actv_to_none(input_df):
    '''Returns a dataframe in which the last activity performed
    by each person is set as 'none'

    Keyword arguments:
    input_df -- dataframe containing trip information
    '''
    df = input_df.copy()

    df['next_person'] = df.person_id.shift(-1)
    df['activity_destination'].loc[(df['person_id'] != df['next_person'])] = 'none'
    df.drop(columns=['next_person'], inplace=True)
    return df

trips = set_last_actv_to_none(trips)
trips.head(13)
```

Out[51]:

	person_id	trip_id	activity_origin	activity_destination	mode_type
0	1	1	sleep	shop	car
1	1	2	shop	none	car
2	2	3	sleep	work	pt
3	2	4	work	none	pt
4	3	5	sleep	sleep	other_mode
5	3	6	sleep	none	other_mode
6	4	7	sleep	school	pt
7	4	8	school	none	pt
8	5	9	sleep	school	car
9	5	10	school	none	car
10	6	11	sleep	other	car
11	6	12	other	sleep	car
12	6	13	sleep	other	car

Now we have to create *count* columns for activity types, as described in the DDAS framework proposition. Those columns indicate how many of each activity have been performed by the agent up to that point in the trip.

In [52]:

```
def create_actv_counts(input_df, input_count):
    '''Returns a dataframe with activity counts columns, which
    represent the number of times each activity has been performed
    up to that point of the trip

    Keyword arguments:
    input_df -- dataframe containing trip information
    input_count -- OHE dataframe of the activities performed, obtained
                  from the input_df
    ...

    df = input_df.copy()
    count = input_count.copy()

    # Transform dataframes into lists of lists for speed performance
    df_list = df.to_numpy()
    count_list = count.to_numpy()

    # If the person_id of the current row is the same of the one on
    # the previous row (if we're dealing with the same activity diary
    # for a certain person) we must sum up the activities that have
    # been performed up to now

    for i in range(1, len(df_list)):
        if (df_list[i,0] == df_list[i-1,0]):
            count_list[i] = count_list[i] + count_list[i-1]
        else:
            pass

    # From the list, we create an output dataframe
    output_df = pd.DataFrame(count_list, columns=count.columns)

    # We set new indexes for both de the original dataframe and
    # the counts dataframe, so they can be concatenated
    df = df.reindex(range(0, len(df)))
    output_df = output_df.reindex(range(0, len(output_df)))

    # The output is the concatenated df
    output_df = pd.concat((df, output_df), axis=1)
    return output_df

# We initiate the activity counts dataframe as the 'one-hot encoded'
# version of the 'activity_origin' column
actv_count = pd.get_dummies(trips['activity_origin'])

trips = create_actv_counts(trips, actv_count)
trips.head()
```

Out[52]:

	person_id	trip_id	activity_origin	activity_destination	mode_type	leisure	other	school	shop	sleep	work
0	1.0	1.0	sleep	shop	car	0	0	0	0	1	0
1	1.0	2.0	shop	none	car	0	0	0	1	1	0
2	2.0	3.0	sleep	work	pt	0	0	0	0	1	0
3	2.0	4.0	work	none	pt	0	0	0	0	1	1
4	3.0	5.0	sleep	sleep	other_mode	0	0	0	0	1	0

We have to rename the count columns to make it easier to understand

In [53]:

```
trips.columns = ['person_id', 'trip_id', 'activity_origin',  
                'activity_destination', 'mode_type', 'count_leisure',  
                'count_other', 'count_school', 'count_shop',  
                'count_sleep', 'count_work']  
  
trips.head()
```

Out[53]:

	person_id	trip_id	activity_origin	activity_destination	mode_type	count_leisure	count_other	count_school	count_shop	count_sleep
0	1.0	1.0	sleep	shop	car	0	0	0	0	1
1	1.0	2.0	shop	none	car	0	0	0	1	1
2	2.0	3.0	sleep	work	pt	0	0	0	0	1
3	2.0	4.0	work	none	pt	0	0	0	0	1
4	3.0	5.0	sleep	sleep	other_mode	0	0	0	0	1

And we do the same for creating the mode counts

In [54]:

```
def create_mode_counts(input_df, input_count):
    '''Returns a dataframe with mode counts columns, which
    represent the number of times each transport mode has been
    used up to that point of the trip

    Keyword arguments:
    input_df -- dataframe containing trip information
    input_count -- OHE dataframe of the mode choice, obtained
                  from the input_df
    ...

    df = input_df.copy()
    count = input_count.copy()

    # The 'count' columns have to be shifted by because we want the
    # counts for the previous trips, not including the current one
    count = count.shift(1)

    # Transform dataframes into lists of lists for speed performance
    df_list = df.to_numpy()
    count_list = count.to_numpy()

    # The first row of the count_list is initiated empty because the
    # first person has not performed any trip yet
    count_list[0] = [0,0,0,0,0]

    for i in range(1,len(df_list)):
        if (df_list[i,0] != df_list[i-1,0]):
            count_list[i] = [0,0,0,0,0]
        else:
            count_list[i] = count_list[i] + count_list[i-1]

    output_df = pd.DataFrame(count_list, columns=count.columns)

    df = df.reindex(range(0,len(df)))
    output_df = output_df.reindex(range(0,len(output_df)))

    output_df = pd.concat((df, output_df), axis=1)
    return output_df

# We initiate the activity counts dataframe as the 'one-hot encoded'
# version of the 'mode_type' column
mode_count = pd.get_dummies(trips['mode_type'])
trips = create_mode_counts(trips, mode_count)
trips.head()
```

Out[54]:

	person_id	trip_id	activity_origin	activity_destination	mode_type	count_leisure	count_other	count_school	count_shop	count_sleep
0	1.0	1.0	sleep	shop	car	0	0	0	0	1
1	1.0	2.0	shop	none	car	0	0	0	1	1
2	2.0	3.0	sleep	work	pt	0	0	0	0	1
3	2.0	4.0	work	none	pt	0	0	0	0	1
4	3.0	5.0	sleep	sleep	other_mode	0	0	0	0	1

Again, we have to rename the count columns

```
In [55]:
trips.columns = ['person_id', 'trip_id', 'activity_origin', 'activity_destination',
                 'mode_type', 'count_leisure', 'count_other', 'count_school',
                 'count_shop', 'count_sleep', 'count_work',
                 'count_bike', 'count_car',
                 'count_other_mode', 'count_pt', 'count_walk']

trips.head()
```

Out[55]:

	person_id	trip_id	activity_origin	activity_destination	mode_type	count_leisure	count_other	count_school	count_shop	count_sleep
0	1.0	1.0	sleep	shop	car	0	0	0	0	1
1	1.0	2.0	shop	none	car	0	0	0	1	1
2	2.0	3.0	sleep	work	pt	0	0	0	0	1
3	2.0	4.0	work	none	pt	0	0	0	0	1
4	3.0	5.0	sleep	sleep	other_mode	0	0	0	0	1

Now we have to One-Hot Encode the columns `activity_origin` and `activity_destination` because they will be used as input for the Decision Tree Classifier and all input to this model must be numerical.

```
In [56]:
trips = pd.concat([trips, pd.get_dummies(trips['activity_origin'], prefix='ohe_origin')], axis=1)
trips = pd.concat([trips, pd.get_dummies(trips['activity_destination'], prefix='ohe_destin')], axis=1)
trips.drop('activity_origin', axis=1, inplace=True)
trips.head()
```

Out[56]:

	person_id	trip_id	activity_destination	mode_type	count_leisure	count_other	count_school	count_shop	count_sleep	count_work	cc
0	1.0	1.0	shop	car	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.
1	1.0	2.0	none	car	0	0	0	1	1	0	0.
2	2.0	3.0	work	pt	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.
3	2.0	4.0	none	pt	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.
4	3.0	5.0	sleep	other_mode	0	0	0	0	1	0	0.

2.4 Creating the input dataframe, training and test sets

Now we merge the `soc`, `reach` and `trips` dataframes

```
In [57]: input_df = pd.merge(soc_and_reach, trips, how='inner', on='person_id')
input_df.drop(['household_id'], axis=1, inplace=True)
input_df.set_index('person_id', inplace=True)

print('The organized input dataframe contains information about '
      + str(len(input_df.index.unique().values))
      + ' individuals and '
      + str(len(input_df))
      + ' trips')

input_df.head()
```

The organized input dataframe contains information about 34340 individuals and 92696 trips

Out[57]:

	age_group	is_female	is_student	education_level	has_driver_license	people_in_household	is_car_available	reach_bike	reach
person_id									
1	11	0	0	4	1	2	1	1502.000000	1043.
1	11	0	0	4	1	2	1	1502.000000	1043.
2	10	1	0	4	0	2	1	1869.333333	1844.
2	10	1	0	4	0	2	1	1869.333333	1844.
3	9	0	0	4	1	4	1	1502.000000	1043.

Let's export this input table as csv

```
In [58]: input_df.to_csv("input_df.csv")
```

In order to create *train* and *test* sets, we will randomly select from the indexes the people who will compose each of these datasets. The proportion will be 80% for training and 20% for testing

```
In [59]: index_list = input_df.index.unique().values
random.Random(123).shuffle(index_list)

# The element in which the test and training sets are separated
# is the one on the first fifth of the list length
separation_element = len(index_list)//5

test_index = index_list[:separation_element]
train_index = index_list[separation_element:]
```

Then, we create train and test dataframes using these index lists

```
In [60]: # Because of the random selection, the trips were out of order,
# so we have to sort them again
test_df = input_df.loc[test_index]
test_df.sort_values(by=['trip_id'], inplace=True)

train_df = input_df.loc[train_index]
train_df.sort_values(by=['trip_id'], inplace=True)
```

We then define which columns are part of the ATM training set and the MCM training set

In [61]:

```
ATM_X_columns = ['age_group',
                 'is_female',
                 'is_student',
                 'education_level',
                 'has_driver_license',
                 'people_in_household',
                 'is_car_available',
                 'reach_bike',
                 'reach_car',
                 'reach_transit',
                 'reach_walk',
                 'count_leisure',
                 'count_other',
                 'count_school',
                 'count_shop',
                 'count_sleep',
                 'count_work',
                 'ohe_origin_leisure',
                 'ohe_origin_other',
                 'ohe_origin_school',
                 'ohe_origin_shop',
                 'ohe_origin_sleep',
                 'ohe_origin_work']

ATM_Y_columns = ['activity_destination']

X_train_ATM = train_df[ATM_X_columns]
Y_train_ATM = train_df[ATM_Y_columns]
```

In [62]:

```
MCM_X_columns = ['age_group',
                 'is_female',
                 'is_student',
                 'education_level',
                 'has_driver_license',
                 'people_in_household',
                 'is_car_available',
                 'reach_bike',
                 'reach_car',
                 'reach_transit',
                 'reach_walk',
                 'count_leisure',
                 'count_other',
                 'count_school',
                 'count_shop',
                 'count_sleep',
                 'count_work',
                 'ohe_origin_leisure',
                 'ohe_origin_other',
                 'ohe_origin_school',
                 'ohe_origin_shop',
                 'ohe_origin_sleep',
                 'ohe_origin_work',
                 'ohe_destin_leisure',
                 'ohe_destin_none',
                 'ohe_destin_other',
                 'ohe_destin_school',
                 'ohe_destin_shop',
                 'ohe_destin_sleep',
                 'ohe_destin_work',
                 'count_bike',
                 'count_car',
                 'count_other_mode',
                 'count_pt',
                 'count_walk']

MCM_Y_columns = ['mode_type']

X_train_MCM = train_df[MCM_X_columns]
Y_train_MCM = train_df[MCM_Y_columns]
```

3. Model 1: Standard DDAS

3.1 Model 1: Specification

Our first implementation is similar to the original DDAS proposition, which defines both ATM and MCM as Decision Tree classifiers. In order to select the optimal maximum tree depth, we will perform cross-validation on the training set. The following code is based on the algorithms presented in <https://towardsdatascience.com/how-to-find-decision-tree-depth-via-cross-validation-2bf143f0f3d6> (<https://towardsdatascience.com/how-to-find-decision-tree-depth-via-cross-validation-2bf143f0f3d6>)

In [63]:

```
def run_cross_validation_on_trees(X, y, tree_depths, cv=5, scoring='f1_micro'):
    """ A function to perform the cross-validation procedure
    for selecting the best specification of the model

    Keyword arguments:
    X -- features used as input
    y -- features that has to be predicted
    tree_depths -- list of integers to be used as tree depths
                  in cross-validation
    cv -- number of folds (default = 5)
    scoring -- scoring function to be used as evaluation metric
    """

    cv_scores_list = []
    cv_scores_std = []
    cv_scores_mean = []
    accuracy_scores = []

    for depth in tree_depths:
        tree_model = DecisionTreeClassifier(max_depth=depth, random_state=123)
        cv_scores = cross_val_score(tree_model, X, y, cv=cv, scoring=scoring)
        cv_scores_list.append(cv_scores)
        cv_scores_mean.append(cv_scores.mean())
        cv_scores_std.append(cv_scores.std())
        accuracy_scores.append(tree_model.fit(X, y).score(X, y))

    cv_scores_mean = np.array(cv_scores_mean)
    cv_scores_std = np.array(cv_scores_std)
    accuracy_scores = np.array(accuracy_scores)

    return cv_scores_mean, cv_scores_std, accuracy_scores
```

We also define a function to visualize those results

In [64]:

```
def plot_cross_validation_on_trees(depths, cv_scores_mean, cv_scores_std, accuracy_scores, title, score):
    """Returns a plot with the results from cross validation
    """

    fig, ax = plt.subplots(1,1, figsize=(12,6))
    ax.plot(depths, cv_scores_mean, '-o', label='mean cross-validation score', alpha=0.9)
    ax.fill_between(depths, cv_scores_mean-2*cv_scores_std, cv_scores_mean+2*cv_scores_std, alpha=0.2)
    ylim = plt.ylim()
    ax.plot(depths, accuracy_scores, '-*', label='train score', alpha=0.9)
    ax.set_title(title, fontsize=16)
    ax.set_xlabel('Tree depth', fontsize=14)
    ax.set_ylabel(score, fontsize=14)
    ax.set_ylim(ylim)
    ax.set_xticks(depths)
    ax.legend()
```

We first run these codes for the ATM model

```

In [66]:
depths_list = range(1,51)

init_time = time.time()
ATM_dt_cv_scores_mean, ATM_dt_cv_scores_std, ATM_dt_accuracy_scores = run_cross_validation_on_trees(X_train
_ATM,
_Y_train
depths_
list)
end_time = time.time()
ellapsed_time = end_time - init_time

print('Cross-validation took ' + str(ellapsed_time) + ' seconds to run')

#plotting accuracy
plot_cross_validation_on_trees(depths_list,
ATM_dt_cv_scores_mean,
ATM_dt_cv_scores_std,
ATM_dt_accuracy_scores,
'F1 score per decision tree depth on ATM cross-validation data',
'f1-score')

```

Cross-validation took 244.91212368011475 seconds to run


```

In [67]:
max_f1 = np.amax(np.around(ATM_dt_cv_scores_mean,3))

optimal_depth_ATM = np.argmax(np.around(ATM_dt_cv_scores_mean,3)) + 1

print('The maximum F1 score for the ATM model is '
+ str(max_f1)
+ ' for tree depth '
+ str(optimal_depth_ATM))

```

The maximum F1 score for the ATM model is 0.637 for tree depth 6

Let's check the confusion matrix for the model with optimal tree depth

In [68]:

```
X_train_cv_ATM, X_val_ATM, Y_train_cv_ATM, Y_val_ATM = train_test_split(X_train_ATM,
                                                                    Y_train_ATM,
                                                                    test_size = 0.20,
                                                                    random_state=123)

ATM_dt_cv_model = DecisionTreeClassifier(max_depth=optimal_depth_ATM, random_state=123)
ATM_dt_cv_model.fit(X_train_cv_ATM, Y_train_cv_ATM)

Y_pred_val_ATM = ATM_dt_cv_model.predict(X_val_ATM)

class_names = ['leisure', 'none', 'other', 'school', 'shop', 'sleep', 'work']

disp = plot_confusion_matrix(ATM_dt_cv_model, X_val_ATM, Y_val_ATM,
                             display_labels=class_names,
                             cmap=plt.cm.Blues,
                             normalize=None)

disp.ax_.set_title('ATM confusion matrix')
plt.show()

print(classification_report(Y_val_ATM, Y_pred_val_ATM, digits=3, labels=class_names))
```



```
/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/sklearn/metrics/_classification.py:1221: UndefinedMetricWarning: Precision and F-score are ill-defined and being set to 0.0 in labels with no predicted samples. Use `zero_division` parameter to control this behavior.
  _warn_prf(average, modifier, msg_start, len(result))
```

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
leisure	0.000	0.000	0.000	278
none	0.680	0.981	0.803	5559
other	0.504	0.266	0.348	2493
school	0.743	0.701	0.722	1095
shop	0.000	0.000	0.000	648
sleep	0.000	0.000	0.000	1407
work	0.585	0.784	0.670	3305
accuracy			0.641	14785
macro avg	0.359	0.390	0.363	14785
weighted avg	0.527	0.641	0.564	14785

We do the same for the MCM module

In [69]:

```
init_time = time.time()
MCM_dt_cv_scores_mean, MCM_dt_cv_scores_std, MCM_dt_accuracy_scores = run_cross_validation_on_trees(X_train
_MCM,
                                                    Y_train
_MCM,
                                                    depths_
list)
end_time = time.time()
ellapsed_time = end_time - init_time

print('Cross-validation took ' + str(ellapsed_time) + ' seconds to run')

# plotting accuracy
plot_cross_validation_on_trees(depths_list,
                               MCM_dt_cv_scores_mean,
                               MCM_dt_cv_scores_std,
                               MCM_dt_accuracy_scores,
                               'F1 score per decision tree depth on MCM cross-validation data',
                               'f1-score')
```

Cross-validation took 297.65575075149536 seconds to run

In [70]:

```
max_f1 = np.amax(np.around(MCM_dt_cv_scores_mean,3))

optimal_depth_MCM = np.argmax(np.around(MCM_dt_cv_scores_mean,3)) + 1

print('The maximum F1 score for the MCM model is '
      + str(max_f1)
      + ' for tree depth '
      + str(optimal_depth_MCM))
```

The maximum F1 score for the MCM model is 0.821 for tree depth 10

In [71]:

```
X_train_cv_MCM, X_val_MCM, Y_train_cv_MCM, Y_val_MCM = train_test_split(X_train_MCM,
                                                                           Y_train_MCM,
                                                                           test_size = 0.20,
                                                                           random_state=123)

MCM_dt_cv_model = DecisionTreeClassifier(max_depth=optimal_depth_MCM, random_state=123)
MCM_dt_cv_model.fit(X_train_cv_MCM, Y_train_cv_MCM)

Y_pred_val_MCM = MCM_dt_cv_model.predict(X_val_MCM)

class_names = ['bike', 'car', 'other_mode', 'pt', 'walk']

disp = plot_confusion_matrix(MCM_dt_cv_model, X_val_MCM, Y_val_MCM,
                             display_labels=class_names,
                             cmap=plt.cm.Blues,
                             normalize=None)

disp.ax_.set_title('MCM confusion matrix, without normalization')
plt.show()

print(classification_report(Y_val_MCM, Y_pred_val_MCM, digits=3, labels=class_names))
```


So we train both the ATM and the MCM modules using the optimal configuration we found and the whole training set

In [72]:

```
init_time = time.time()

ATM_dt_model = DecisionTreeClassifier(max_depth=optimal_depth_ATM, random_state=123)
ATM_dt_model.fit(X_train_ATM, Y_train_ATM)

MCM_dt_model = DecisionTreeClassifier(max_depth=optimal_depth_MCM, random_state=123)
MCM_dt_model.fit(X_train_MCM, Y_train_MCM)

end_time = time.time()
ellapsed_time = end_time - init_time

print('Model training for both the ATM and MCM took ' + str(ellapsed_time) + ' seconds to run')
```

Model training for both the ATM and MCM took 1.1111485958099365 seconds to run

3.2 Model 1: Inference

3.2.1 Organizing X_test

Our current `test_df` table contains a lot of information that we won't need during the inference process. This is because the dataframe already contains all the 'answers', the complete activity diaries for each person. Our goal is to use the DDAS framework to predict those diaries. Therefore, we have to create a `X_test` dataframe containing only the required information for each person, so the model can predict their diaries

In [73]:

```
X_test_columns = ['age_group',
                  'is_female',
                  'is_student',
                  'education_level',
                  'has_driver_license',
                  'people_in_household',
                  'is_car_available',
                  'reach_bike',
                  'reach_car',
                  'reach_transit',
                  'reach_walk']

X_test = test_df[X_test_columns].copy()

# We have to drop duplicate columns because the same person
# appears on multiple rows, as the original dataset contained
# all trips that person performed
X_test.reset_index(inplace=True)
X_test.drop_duplicates(inplace=True)
X_test.set_index('person_id', inplace=True)
X_test.head()
```

Out[73]:

	age_group	is_female	is_student	education_level	has_driver_license	people_in_household	is_car_available	reach_bike	reach_
person_id									
6	8	1	0	7	1	4	1	1502.000000	1043.
34	6	1	1	8	1	5	1	4201.666667	1829.
37	7	0	0	9	1	3	1	3015.666667	1260.
39	11	0	0	5	1	3	1	3015.666667	1260.
54	4	0	1	7	0	3	1	4639.666667	2259.

3.2.2 Building the inference framework

Now we will define a *Person* object, which will be useful during the inference phase. Each person has individual attributes such as soc features, activity and mode counts, current and next activity, etc.

In [74]:

```
class Person:
    def __init__(self, soc_features):
        self.id = soc_features.index # Series type
        self.soc_features = soc_features

        self.origin_act_type = 'sleep' # String
        self.origin_act_type_ohc = pd.DataFrame(data={'ohc_origin_leisure':[0],
                                                    'ohc_origin_other':[0],
                                                    'ohc_origin_school':[0],
                                                    'ohc_origin_shop':[0],
                                                    'ohc_origin_sleep':[1],
                                                    'ohc_origin_work':[0]},
                                                index=self.id)

        self.destination_act_type = '' # String
        self.destination_act_type_ohc = pd.DataFrame(data={'ohc_destin_leisure':[0],
                                                            'ohc_destin_other':[0],
                                                            'ohc_destin_none':[0],
                                                            'ohc_destin_school':[0],
                                                            'ohc_destin_shop':[0],
                                                            'ohc_destin_sleep':[0],
                                                            'ohc_destin_work':[0]},
                                                        index=self.id)

        self.act_type_counts = pd.DataFrame(data={'count_leisure':[0],
                                                  'count_other':[0],
                                                  'count_school':[0],
                                                  'count_shop':[0],
                                                  'count_sleep':[1],
                                                  'count_work':[0]},
                                              index=self.id)

        self.mode_counts = pd.DataFrame(data={'count_bike':[0],
                                              'count_car':[0],
                                              'count_other_mode':[0],
                                              'count_pt':[0],
                                              'count_walk':[0]},
                                          index=self.id)

        self.cur_mode = '' # String

        self.total_trips = 0

    def update_act_counts(self):
        if self.destination_act_type == 'none':
            pass

        else:
            self.act_type_counts.loc[:, 'count_'+self.destination_act_type] = self.act_type_counts.loc[:, 'count_'+self.destination_act_type] + 1

    def update_destination_act_type_ohc(self):
        self.destination_act_type_ohc = pd.DataFrame(data={'ohc_destin_leisure':[0],
                                                            'ohc_destin_none':[0],
                                                            'ohc_destin_other':[0],
                                                            'ohc_destin_school':[0],
                                                            'ohc_destin_shop':[0],
                                                            'ohc_destin_sleep':[0],
                                                            'ohc_destin_work':[0]},
                                                        index=self.id)

        self.destination_act_type_ohc.loc[:, 'ohc_destin_' + self.destination_act_type] = self.destination_act_type_ohc.loc[:, 'ohc_destin_' + self.destination_act_type] + 1

    def update_mode_counts(self):
```

```

self.mode_counts.loc[:, 'count_'+self.cur_mode] = self.mode_counts.loc[:, 'count_'+self.cur_mode] + 1

def update_origin(self):
    self.origin_act_type_ohe = pd.DataFrame(data={'ohe_origin_leisure':[0],
                                                'ohe_origin_other':[0],
                                                'ohe_origin_school':[0],
                                                'ohe_origin_shop':[0],
                                                'ohe_origin_sleep':[0],
                                                'ohe_origin_work':[0]},
                                             index=self.id)
    self.origin_act_type_ohe.loc[:, 'ohe_origin_' + self.destination_act_type] = 1
    self.origin_act_type = self.destination_act_type

```

The next function summarizes the DDAS framework. We use the trained ATM and MCM models to make inferences about the activity diaries for each person on a `X_test` dataframe

In [75]:

```
def ddas_framework(X_test, ATM_model, MCM_model):
    # We start by initiating an empty df for the results

    results = pd.DataFrame(columns=['person_id',
                                    'destination',
                                    'mode'])

    results = results.set_index('person_id')

    for i in range(0, len(X_test)):

        # For each row of the X_test dataframe we define a
        # new Person object
        person = Person(X_test[i:i+1].copy())

        # Here we set a hard-coded limit so no agent can have
        # more than 12 trips in their activity diary
        while(person.destination_act_type != 'none'):
            if person.total_trips == 12:
                person.destination_act_type = 'none'

            # If the person has not conducted 12 trips yet, let's
            # predict the next trip
            else:
                ATM_input = pd.concat([person.soc_features,
                                        person.act_type_counts,
                                        person.origin_act_type_ohc],
                                        axis = 1)

                person.destination_act_type = ATM_model.predict(ATM_input)[0]

            person.update_destination_act_type_ohc()

            MCM_input = pd.concat([ATM_input,
                                    person.destination_act_type_ohc,
                                    person.mode_counts],
                                    axis = 1)

            person.cur_mode = MCM_model.predict(MCM_input)[0]

            result_row = pd.DataFrame(data={'destination':[person.destination_act_type],
                                            'mode':[person.cur_mode]},
                                      index=person.id)

            results = results.append(result_row)

            person.update_act_counts()
            person.update_mode_counts()
            person.update_origin()
            person.total_trips = person.total_trips + 1

    return results
```

3.2.3 Using the trained models to make predictions

Now we will run the DDAS framework using the three machine learning models that we have trained to make predictions on the *X_test* dataset

In [76]:

```
init_time = time.time()

results_dt = ddas_framework(X_test, ATM_dt_model, MCM_dt_model)

end_time = time.time()
ellapsed_time = end_time - init_time

print('The DDAS framework took ' + str(ellapsed_time) + ' seconds to run')
```

The DDAS framework took 204.29671096801758 seconds to run

3.3 Model 1: Evaluation

3.3.1 ATM Model

a) Expected and observed distribution of trips

The first thing we will analyse on the results obtained from the DDAS framework is the distribution of trips

In [77]:

```
observed_list = round(results_dt.destination.value_counts()*100/len(results_dt), 6)
observed_list
```

Out[77]:

```
none      49.959991
work      32.698043
other      9.769404
school     7.565287
shop       0.007274
Name: destination, dtype: float64
```

In [78]:

```
expected_list = round(test_df[['activity_destination', 'mode_type']].activity_destination.value_counts()*100/len(test_df), 6)
expected_list
```

Out[78]:

```
none      36.584456
work      22.505726
other      17.258829
sleep      9.668140
school     7.068662
shop       4.772812
leisure   2.141373
Name: activity_destination, dtype: float64
```

In [79]:

```
def plot_expected_and_observed(input_expected, input_observed, x_label, y_label, legend, color, dist=0):
    '''Returns plots of the given lists

    Keyword arguments:
    input_expected -- list of the expected values of each category
    input_observed -- list of the observed values of each category
    '''

    fig, axs = plt.subplots(figsize=(10, 5))

    chart_title = ''
    df = pd.concat([input_expected, input_observed], axis=1)

    N = len(df)
    ind = np.arange(N) # the x locations for the groups
    width = 0.25

    x = df.index

    y_expected = df.iloc[:,0]
    rects_expected = axs.bar(ind, y_expected, width, color='lightgreen')

    y_observed = df.iloc[:,1]
    rects_observed = axs.bar(ind+width, y_observed, width, color=color)

    axs.set_title(chart_title)
    axs.set_ylabel(y_label, fontsize=12)
    axs.set_xlabel(x_label, fontsize=12)
    axs.set_xticks(ind+width)
    axs.set_xticklabels(x)
    axs.legend((rects_expected[0], rects_observed[0]), ('expected', legend), loc=1)

    def autolabel(rects, offset=0):
        for rect in rects:
            try:
                h = rect.get_height()
                if (h >= 0.1):
                    axs.text(rect.get_x()+rect.get_width()/2 + offset, 1.00*h, '%g'%round(h,1),
                             ha='center', va='bottom')
            else:
                axs.text(rect.get_x()+rect.get_width()/2 + offset, 1.00*h, '%g'%round(h,3),
                             ha='center', va='bottom')
        except:
            pass

    autolabel(rects_expected, -dist)
    autolabel(rects_observed, +dist)

plot_expected_and_observed(expected_list, observed_list, 'activity types', 'proportion (%)', 'Model 1', 'lightblue', dist=0.05)
```


b) Expected and observed frequency of chains

In [80]:

```
def get_actv_chains(input_df):
    '''Returns a list with the activity chains performed by each person
    (e.g. H-W-N refers to chain home-work-none)

    Keyword arguments:
    input_df -- dataframe with trip information
    '''
    df = input_df.reset_index()

    chains_list = dict.fromkeys(df.iloc[:,0].unique())
    df_list = df.to_numpy()

    try:
        # Read each row of the input dataframe
        for i in range(0, len(df_list)):
            # If the person id is different from the previous
            if (df_list[i,0] != df_list[i-1,0]):
                #The chain of activities for the person is initiated at home
                chains_list[df_list[i,0]] = 'home-'+df_list[i,1]
            # If is the same person of the previous row computed
            else:
                # The chain is updated with a new activity
                chains_list[df_list[i,0]] = chains_list[df_list[i,0]]+'-'+df_list[i,1]
    # Exception to deal with the first row
    except:
        chains_list[df_list[i,0]] = 'home-'+df_list[i,1]

    return chains_list
```

```
In [81]: chains_test = pd.Series(get_actv_chains(test_df[['activity_destination', 'mode_type']]))
chains_test.value_counts().head(30)
```

```
Out[81]:
home-work-none                2467
home-other-none               915
home-school-none             789
home-shop-none               347
home-other-sleep-other-none  194
home-work-sleep-work-none    185
home-leisure-none           155
home-other-other-none        79
home-work-sleep-other-none   73
home-work-other-none         69
home-work-school-none        68
home-work-sleep-school-none  68
home-work-shop-work-none     50
home-work-work-none          45
home-other-work-none         43
home-other-work-other-none   41
home-other-sleep-work-none   40
home-work-sleep-leisure-none 37
home-school-work-none        33
home-sleep-none              30
home-school-sleep-work-none  29
home-school-sleep-school-none 29
home-work-sleep-shop-none    27
home-other-shop-none         27
home-other-sleep-shop-none   26
home-school-sleep-other-none 26
home-other-sleep-other-sleep-other-none 24
home-shop-sleep-other-none   23
home-other-other-sleep-other-none 20
home-work-shop-none          20
dtype: int64
```

```
In [82]: len(chains_test.unique())
```

```
Out[82]: 454
```

```
In [83]: chains_dt = pd.Series(get_actv_chains(results_dt))
chains_dt.value_counts()
```

```
Out[83]:
home-work-none                4495
home-other-none              1331
home-school-none             1040
home-other-other-other-other-other-other-other-other-other-other-none 1
home-shop-none                1
dtype: int64
```

```
In [84]: len(chains_dt.unique())
```

```
Out[84]: 5
```

In [85]:

```
def get_actv_chain_legnths(input_df):
    '''Returns a list the length of chain of activities
    performed by each person
    (e.g.: home-work-home is a chain of size = 2
    because there are two trips: home-work and
    work-home)

    Keyword arguments:
    input_df -- dataframe with trip information
    ...

    df = input_df.reset_index()

    len_list = dict.fromkeys(df.iloc[:,0].unique())
    df_list = df.to_numpy()

    try:
        # Read each row of the input dataframe
        for i in range(0,len(df_list)):
            # If the person id is different from the previous
            if (df_list[i,0] != df_list[i-1,0]):
                #The length of the person's chain is initiated at one
                len_list[df_list[i,0]] = 1

                # If it is the same person of the previous row computed
            else:
                # The chain is updated with a new activity
                len_list[df_list[i,0]] = len_list[df_list[i,0]] + 1
        # Exception to deal with the first row
    except:
        len_list[df_list[i,0]] = 1

    return len_list
```

In [86]:

```
len_chains_test = pd.Series(get_actv_chain_legnths(test_df[['activity_destination','mode_type']]))
len_chains_test.value_counts()
```

Out[86]:

```
2    4703
4    1100
3     515
6     232
5     177
7      61
8      49
9      13
10     10
11      3
14      2
23      1
13      1
12      1
dtype: int64
```

In [87]:

```
len_chains_dt = pd.Series(get_actv_chain_legnths(results_dt))
len_chains_dt.value_counts()
```

Out[87]:

```
2    6867
13      1
dtype: int64
```

In [88]:

```
plot_expected_and_observed(len_chains_test.value_counts(), len_chains_dt.value_counts(), 'chain length', 'counts', 'Model 1', 'lightblue', dist=0.075)
```


c) Importance of features

In [89]:

```
feature_importances = permutation_importance(ATM_dt_model,
                                             X_train_ATM,
                                             Y_train_ATM,
                                             scoring='f1_micro',
                                             n_repeats=5,
                                             random_state=123)

col1 = feature_importances.importances_mean
col2 = ATM_X_columns

df = pd.DataFrame(col1, index=col2, columns=['importance'])
df.sort_values(by='importance', ascending=False, inplace=True)
df
```

Out[89]:

	importance
ohe_origin_sleep	0.298876
is_student	0.070084
age_group	0.020070
is_female	0.010928
reach_bike	0.010492
education_level	0.005790
reach_car	0.000942
has_driver_license	0.000317
people_in_household	0.000084
ohe_origin_other	0.000068
reach_transit	0.000041
count_work	0.000022
ohe_origin_shop	0.000000
ohe_origin_school	0.000000
ohe_origin_leisure	0.000000
count_leisure	0.000000
count_sleep	0.000000
count_shop	0.000000
count_school	0.000000
count_other	0.000000
reach_walk	0.000000
is_car_available	0.000000
ohe_origin_work	0.000000

d) VALFRAM activity count validation

In [90]:

```
def actv_count_validation(input_df):
    '''Returns a dictionary with activity types as keys and
    frequency counts of those activities as values

    Keyword arguments:
    input_df -- dataframe containing trip information
    ...

    # Gets dataframe as input, turns index into column and renames columns
    df = input_df.copy()
    df.reset_index(inplace=True)
    df.columns = ['person_id', 'destination', 'mode']

    # Creates a dictionary with the keys being the number of times that the
    # activity is performed
    count_dict = {}
    activity_list = ['other', 'sleep', 'none', 'school', 'work', 'shop', 'leisure']
    for activity_type in activity_list:
        count_dict[activity_type] = {1:0,2:0,3:0,4:0,
                                     5:0,6:0,7:0,8:0,9:0,
                                     10:0,11:0,12:0}

    # Creates a new dataframe from the count of how many times each person performs
    # each type of activity. Renames the columns of this new dataframe
    x = pd.DataFrame(df.groupby(['person_id', 'destination'])['destination'].count())
    x.rename(columns={"destination": "counts"}, inplace=True)

    # From the previous dataframe, creates a new count of how many people perform
    # a certain number of times each activity. For instance, how many people perform
    # only 1 time the 'work' activity, etc
    y = x.groupby(['destination', 'counts'])['counts'].count()

    # Puts those results into the dictionary
    for activity in df.destination.unique():
        for key in y.loc[activity].index:
            count_dict[activity][key] = y.loc[activity][key]
            residual = len(df.person_id.unique()) - sum(count_dict[activity].values())
            count_dict[activity].update({0: residual})

    return count_dict
```

In [91]:

```
activ_counts_dt = actv_count_validation(results_dt)
activ_counts_test = actv_count_validation(test_df[['activity_destination', 'mode_type']])
```

We have also to write a function to compute chi-square values from the dictionaries that were created.

In [92]:

```
def compute_chi_square_from_values(input_expected, input_observed):
    '''Returns a list containing partial chi-square values for each
    parameter being computed (activities or models) and a total
    chi-square value being the sum of those partials.'''

    Keyword arguments:
    input_expected -- dict with expected counts for the parameter
    input_observed -- dict with observed counts for the parameter
    '''

    total_chi_square = 0
    chi_square_list = []

    for key in input_expected:

        expected = pd.Series(input_expected[key], name='expected')
        expected.sort_index(inplace=True)

        observed = pd.Series(input_observed[key], name='observed')
        observed.sort_index(inplace=True)

        chi_square = ((expected-observed-1).pow(2))/expected
        chi_square[np.isnan(chi_square)] = 0

        total_chi_square = total_chi_square + sum(chi_square.replace(np.inf,0))

        chi_square.rename('chi_square_' + key)
        chi_square_list.append([key, expected, observed, sum(chi_square.replace(np.inf,0))])

    return [total_chi_square, chi_square_list]
```

In [93]:

```
chi_square_activity_counts_dt = compute_chi_square_from_values(activ_counts_test, activ_counts_dt)[0]
print('The total chi-square value for activity counts validation in the decision tree model is '
      + str(chi_square_activity_counts_dt))
```

```
The total chi-square value for activity counts validation in the decision tree model is 4893.28597655631
6
```

We know the total chi-square value, but let's see how the partial totals for each activity type are presented (the first instance of each list is the activity type):

In [94]:

```
chi_square_activ_subtotals = compute_chi_square_from_values(activ_counts_test, activ_counts_dt)[1]
chi_square_activ_subtotals[0]
```

Out[94]:

```
['other',
 0    4673
 1    1465
 2     536
 3     118
 4      55
 5       9
 6       7
 7       2
 8       0
 9       2
10      1
11      0
12      0
Name: expected, dtype: int64,
 0    5536
 1    1331
 2       0
 3       0
 4       0
 5       0
 6       0
 7       0
 8       0
 9       0
10      0
11      0
12      1
Name: observed, dtype: int64,
888.1035226245878]
```

3.3.2 MCM Model

Next on the VALFRAM method, we have the mode choice validation, in which we analyze, for each destination activity type, what is the proportion of trips performed by each transportation mode. For instance, for each 100 trips performed with the purpose of 'leisure', how many of those were conducted by car? And by transit? It is important to compute those values in terms of proportion (for each 100), because we can get comparable chi-square values for the test and validation sets.

In [95]:

```
def mode_count_validation(input_df):
    '''Returns a dictionary with transportation modes as keys and
    frequency counts of those modes as values

    Keyword arguments:
    input_df -- dataframe containing trip information
    '''
    df = input_df.copy()
    df.reset_index(inplace=True)
    df.columns = ['person_id', 'destination', 'mode']

    count_dict = {}
    activity_list = ['other', 'sleep', 'none', 'school', 'work', 'shop', 'leisure']

    for activity_type in activity_list:
        count_dict[activity_type] = {'bike':0,
                                     'car':0,
                                     'other_mode':0,
                                     'pt':0,
                                     'walk':0}

    x = pd.DataFrame(df.groupby(['destination', 'mode'])['mode'].count())

    for activity in df.destination.unique():
        for transp_mode in x.loc[activity].index:
            count_dict[activity][transp_mode] = x.loc[activity].loc[transp_mode][0]

    return count_dict

mode_counts_dt = mode_count_validation(results_dt)
```

In [96]:

```
mode_counts_dt = mode_count_validation(results_dt)
mode_counts_test = mode_count_validation(test_df[['activity_destination', 'mode_type']])
```

We must define another function to compute chi_squared value from proportions

In [97]:

```
def compute_chi_square_from_proportions(input_expected, input_observed):
    '''Returns a list containing partial chi-square values for each
    parameter being computed (activities or models) and a total
    chi-square value being the sum of those partials.

    Keyword arguments:
    input_expected -- dict with expected counts for the parameter
    input_observed -- dict with observed counts for the parameter
    '''

    total_chi_square = 0
    chi_square_list = []

    for key in input_expected:

        total_expected = sum(input_expected[key].values())
        expected_proportions = {k:v/total_expected for (k,v) in input_expected[key].items()}

        total_observed = sum(input_observed[key].values())
        expected_values = {k:round(v*total_observed, 0) for (k,v) in expected_proportions.items()}

        expected = pd.Series(expected_values, name='expected')
        expected.sort_index(inplace=True)

        observed = pd.Series(input_observed[key], name='observed')
        observed.sort_index(inplace=True)

        chi_square = ((expected-observed-1).pow(2))/expected
        chi_square[np.isnan(chi_square)] = 0

        total_chi_square = total_chi_square + sum(chi_square.replace(np.inf,0))

        chi_square.rename('chi_square_' + key)
        chi_square_list.append([key, expected, observed, sum(chi_square.replace(np.inf,0))])

    return [total_chi_square, chi_square_list]
```

In [98]:

```
chi_square_mode_counts = compute_chi_square_from_proportions(mode_counts_test, mode_counts_dt)[0]

print('The total chi-square value for mode counts validation in this set of results is '
      + str(chi_square_mode_counts))
```

The total chi-square value for mode counts validation in this set of results is 1908.9390764352197

Again, let's check how partial values of chi-square are presented

In [99]:

```
chi_square_mode_subtotals = compute_chi_square_from_proportions(mode_counts_test, mode_counts_dt)[1]
chi_square_mode_subtotals[0]
```

Out[99]:

```
['other',
 bike          19.0
 car          817.0
 other_mode    32.0
 pt           163.0
 walk         313.0
Name: expected, dtype: float64,
 bike          0
 car          505
 other_mode    0
 pt           168
 walk         670
Name: observed, dtype: int64,
575.1599459524979]
```

In [100]:

```
def plot_chi_square_results(input_list, label, color):
    '''Returns plots of the given lists

    Keyword arguments:
    input_list -- list to be plotted
    '''

    fig, axs = plt.subplots(4,2,figsize=(20, 30))

    for i in range(0,len(input_list)):

        line = (i//2)
        col = (i%2)-1

        chart_title = input_list[i][0]
        chi_2_value = int(input_list[i][3])
        df = pd.concat([input_list[i][1],input_list[i][2]], axis=1)
        df.drop(df[df.expected == 0].index, inplace=True)

        N = len(df)
        ind = np.arange(N) # the x locations for the groups
        width = 0.25

        x = df.index

        y_expected = df['expected']
        rects_expected = axs[line,col].bar(ind, y_expected, width, color='lightgreen')

        y_observed = df['observed']
        rects_observed = axs[line,col].bar(ind+width, y_observed, width, color=color)

        axs[line,col].set_title(chart_title+', chi square='+str(chi_2_value), fontsize=20)
        axs[line,col].set_ylabel(chart_title+' frequency', fontsize=16)
        axs[line,col].set_xlabel('counts', fontsize=16)
        axs[line,col].set_xticks(ind+width)
        axs[line,col].set_xticklabels(x, fontsize=14)
        axs[line,col].legend((rects_expected, rects_observed), ('expected', label), fontsize=16, loc=1)

    def autolabel(rects):
        for rect in rects:
            h = rect.get_height()
            if (h>0):
                axs[line,col].text(rect.get_x()+rect.get_width()/2., 1*h, '%d'%int(h),
                                   ha='center', va='bottom', fontsize=14)
            else:
                pass

    autolabel(rects_expected)
    autolabel(rects_observed)
```

In [101]:

```
plot_chi_square_results(chi_square_activ_subtotals, 'Model 1', 'lightblue')
```


In [102]:

```
plot_chi_square_results(chi_square_mode_subtotals, 'Model 1', 'lightblue')
```


In [103]:

```
end_notebook = time.time()
total_duration = end_notebook - init_notebook
print('The total duration of this notebook is ' + str(total_duration))
```

The total duration of this notebook is 1859.4057874679565

4. Model 2: improving the Decision Tree Classifier

4.1 Testing a different score function

In [104]:

```
init_time = time.time()
ATM_dt_cv_scores_mean, ATM_dt_cv_scores_std, ATM_dt_accuracy_scores = run_cross_validation_on_trees(X_train
_ATM,
_Y_train
_ATM,
depths_
list,
scoring
='balanced_accuracy')
end_time = time.time()
ellapsed_time = end_time - init_time

print('Cross-validation took ' + str(ellapsed_time) + ' seconds to run')

# plotting accuracy
plot_cross_validation_on_trees(depths_list,
ATM_dt_cv_scores_mean,
ATM_dt_cv_scores_std,
ATM_dt_accuracy_scores,
'Balanced accuracy score per decision tree depth on ATM cross-validation dat
a',
'balanced accuracy')
```

Cross-validation took 225.26505970954895 seconds to run

In [105]:

```
max_balanced_accuracy = np.amax(np.around(ATM_dt_cv_scores_mean,3))

optimal_depth_ATM = np.argmax(np.around(ATM_dt_cv_scores_mean,3)) + 1

print('The maximum balanced_accuracy score for the ATM model is '
      + str(max_balanced_accuracy)
      + ' for tree depth '
      + str(optimal_depth_ATM))
```

The maximum balanced_accuracy score for the ATM model is 0.394 for tree depth 10

In [106]:

```
X_train_cv_ATM, X_val_ATM, Y_train_cv_ATM, Y_val_ATM = train_test_split(X_train_ATM,
                                                                      Y_train_ATM,
                                                                      test_size = 0.20,
                                                                      random_state=123)

ATM_dt_cv_model = DecisionTreeClassifier(max_depth=optimal_depth_ATM, random_state=123)
ATM_dt_cv_model.fit(X_train_cv_ATM, Y_train_cv_ATM)

Y_pred_val_ATM = ATM_dt_cv_model.predict(X_val_ATM)

class_names = ['leisure', 'none', 'other', 'school', 'shop', 'sleep', 'work']

disp = plot_confusion_matrix(ATM_dt_cv_model, X_val_ATM, Y_val_ATM,
                             display_labels=class_names,
                             cmap=plt.cm.Blues,
                             normalize=None)

disp.ax_.set_title('ATM confusion matrix')
plt.show()

print(classification_report(Y_val_ATM, Y_pred_val_ATM, digits=3, labels=class_names))
```


	precision	recall	f1-score	support
leisure	0.000	0.000	0.000	278
none	0.683	0.956	0.797	5559
other	0.486	0.331	0.393	2493
school	0.747	0.674	0.709	1095
shop	0.289	0.037	0.066	648
sleep	0.275	0.031	0.056	1407
work	0.610	0.751	0.673	3305
accuracy			0.637	14785
macro avg	0.441	0.397	0.385	14785
weighted avg	0.569	0.637	0.577	14785

In [107]:

```
init_time = time.time()
MCM_dt_cv_scores_mean, MCM_dt_cv_scores_std, MCM_dt_accuracy_scores = run_cross_validation_on_trees(X_train
_MCM,
_Y_train
_MCM,
depths_
list,
scoring
='balanced_accuracy')
end_time = time.time()
ellapsed_time = end_time - init_time

print('Cross-validation took ' + str(ellapsed_time) + ' seconds to run')

# plotting accuracy
plot_cross_validation_on_trees(depths_list,
MCM_dt_cv_scores_mean,
MCM_dt_cv_scores_std,
MCM_dt_accuracy_scores,
'Balanced accuracy per decision tree depth on MCM cross-validation data',
'balanced_accuracy')
```

Cross-validation took 278.6355199813843 seconds to run

In [108]:

```
max_balanced_accuracy = np.amax(np.around(MCM_dt_cv_scores_mean,3))

optimal_depth_MCM = np.argmax(np.around(MCM_dt_cv_scores_mean,3)) + 1

print('The maximum balanced accuracy score for the MCM model is '
+ str(max_balanced_accuracy)
+ ' for tree depth '
+ str(optimal_depth_MCM))
```

The maximum balanced accuracy score for the MCM model is 0.684 for tree depth 10

4.2 Model 2: Training with the SMOTE technique

```
In [109]: X_train_cv_ATM, X_val_ATM, Y_train_cv_ATM, Y_val_ATM = train_test_split(X_train_ATM,
                                                                           Y_train_ATM,
                                                                           test_size = 0.20,
                                                                           random_state=123)
```

```
In [110]: sm = SMOTE(random_state=123)
X_train_cv_smote_ATM, Y_train_cv_smote_ATM = sm.fit_resample(X_train_cv_ATM, Y_train_cv_ATM)
```

```
In [111]: init_time = time.time()
ATM_dt_cv_scores_mean, ATM_dt_cv_scores_std, ATM_dt_accuracy_scores = run_cross_validation_on_trees(X_train_cv_smote_ATM,
                                                                                                    Y_train_cv_smote_ATM,
                                                                                                    depths_list,
                                                                                                    scoring='balanced_accuracy')
end_time = time.time()
ellapsed_time = end_time - init_time

print('Cross-validation took ' + str(ellapsed_time) + ' seconds to run')

# plotting accuracy
plot_cross_validation_on_trees(depths_list,
                                ATM_dt_cv_scores_mean,
                                ATM_dt_cv_scores_std,
                                ATM_dt_accuracy_scores,
                                'Balanced accuracy per decision tree depth on ATM cross-validation data',
                                'balanced-accuracy')
```

Cross-validation took 503.42961072921753 seconds to run

In [112]:

```
max_balanced_accuracy = np.amax(np.around(ATM_dt_cv_scores_mean,3))

optimal_depth_ATM = np.argmax(np.around(ATM_dt_cv_scores_mean,3)) + 1

print('The maximum balanced_accuracy score for the ATM model is '
      + str(max_balanced_accuracy)
      + ' for tree depth '
      + str(optimal_depth_ATM))
```

The maximum balanced_accuracy score for the ATM model is 0.693 for tree depth 30

In [113]:

```
ATM_dt_cv_model = DecisionTreeClassifier(max_depth=optimal_depth_ATM, random_state=123)
ATM_dt_cv_model.fit(X_train_cv_smote_ATM,
                    Y_train_cv_smote_ATM)

Y_pred_val_ATM = ATM_dt_cv_model.predict(X_val_ATM)

class_names = ['leisure', 'none', 'other', 'school', 'shop', 'sleep', 'work']

disp = plot_confusion_matrix(ATM_dt_cv_model, X_val_ATM, Y_val_ATM,
                             display_labels=class_names,
                             cmap=plt.cm.Blues,
                             normalize=None)

disp.ax_.set_title('ATM confusion matrix')
plt.show()

print(classification_report(Y_val_ATM, Y_pred_val_ATM, digits=3, labels=class_names))
```


	precision	recall	f1-score	support
leisure	0.033	0.076	0.046	278
none	0.706	0.602	0.650	5559
other	0.350	0.372	0.361	2493
school	0.531	0.563	0.547	1095
shop	0.122	0.198	0.151	648
sleep	0.211	0.286	0.243	1407
work	0.547	0.439	0.487	3305
accuracy			0.466	14785
macro avg	0.357	0.362	0.355	14785
weighted avg	0.512	0.466	0.485	14785

```
In [114]: X_train_cv_MCM, X_val_MCM, Y_train_cv_MCM, Y_val_MCM = train_test_split(X_train_MCM,
                                                                           Y_train_MCM,
                                                                           test_size = 0.20,
                                                                           random_state=123)
```

```
In [115]: X_train_cv_smote_MCM, Y_train_cv_smote_MCM = sm.fit_resample(X_train_cv_MCM, Y_train_cv_MCM)
```

```
In [116]: init_time = time.time()
MCM_dt_cv_scores_mean, MCM_dt_cv_scores_std, MCM_dt_accuracy_scores = run_cross_validation_on_trees(X_train_cv_smote_MCM,
                                                                                                  Y_train_cv_smote_MCM,
                                                                                                  depths_list,
                                                                                                  scoring='balanced_accuracy')
end_time = time.time()
ellapsed_time = end_time - init_time

print('Cross-validation took ' + str(ellapsed_time) + ' seconds to run')

# plotting accuracy
plot_cross_validation_on_trees(depths_list,
                               MCM_dt_cv_scores_mean,
                               MCM_dt_cv_scores_std,
                               MCM_dt_accuracy_scores,
                               'Balanced accuracy per decision tree depth on MCM cross-validation data',
                               'balanced accuracy')
```

Cross-validation took 608.8228871822357 seconds to run

In [117]:

```
max_balanced_accuracy = np.amax(np.around(MCM_dt_cv_scores_mean,3))

optimal_depth_MCM = np.argmax(np.around(MCM_dt_cv_scores_mean,3)) + 1

print('The maximum balanced accuracy score for the MCM model is '
      + str(max_balanced_accuracy)
      + ' for tree depth '
      + str(optimal_depth_MCM))
```

The maximum balanced accuracy score for the MCM model is 0.871 for tree depth 37

In [118]:

```
MCM_dt_cv_model = DecisionTreeClassifier(max_depth=optimal_depth_MCM, random_state=123)
MCM_dt_cv_model.fit(X_train_cv_smote_MCM,
                    Y_train_cv_smote_MCM)

Y_pred_val_MCM = MCM_dt_cv_model.predict(X_val_MCM)

class_names = ['bike', 'car', 'other_mode', 'pt', 'walk']

disp = plot_confusion_matrix(MCM_dt_cv_model, X_val_MCM, Y_val_MCM,
                             display_labels=class_names,
                             cmap=plt.cm.Blues,
                             normalize=None)

disp.ax_.set_title('MCM confusion matrix, without normalization')
plt.show()

print(classification_report(Y_val_MCM, Y_pred_val_MCM, digits=3, labels=class_names))
```


	precision	recall	f1-score	support
bike	0.470	0.566	0.513	274
car	0.839	0.809	0.824	7092
other_mode	0.394	0.487	0.436	604
pt	0.712	0.727	0.720	3526
walk	0.722	0.717	0.720	3289
accuracy			0.751	14785
macro avg	0.627	0.661	0.642	14785
weighted avg	0.758	0.751	0.754	14785

In [119]:

```
init_time = time.time()

X_train_ATM_smote, Y_train_ATM_smote = sm.fit_resample(X_train_ATM, Y_train_ATM)
ATM_dt_model_smote = DecisionTreeClassifier(max_depth=optimal_depth_ATM, random_state=123)
ATM_dt_model_smote.fit(X_train_ATM_smote, Y_train_ATM_smote)

X_train_MCM_smote, Y_train_MCM_smote = sm.fit_resample(X_train_MCM, Y_train_MCM)
MCM_dt_model_smote = DecisionTreeClassifier(max_depth=optimal_depth_MCM, random_state=123)
MCM_dt_model_smote.fit(X_train_MCM_smote, Y_train_MCM_smote)

end_time = time.time()
ellapsed_time = end_time - init_time

print('Model training for both the ATM and MCM took ' + str(ellapsed_time) + ' seconds to run')
```

Model training for both the ATM and MCM took 9.33354115486145 seconds to run

4.3 Model 2: Inference

In [120]:

```
init_time = time.time()

results_smote = ddas_framework(X_test, ATM_dt_model_smote, MCM_dt_model_smote)

end_time = time.time()
ellapsed_time = end_time - init_time

print('The DDAS framework with SMOTE took ' + str(ellapsed_time) + ' seconds to run')
```

The DDAS framework with SMOTE took 370.22284865379333 seconds to run

4.4 Model 2: Evaluation

4.4.1 ATM Model

a) Expected and observed distribution of trips

The first thing we will analyse on the results obtained from Model 2 is the distribution of trips

In [121]:

```
observed_list_smote = round(results_smote.destination.value_counts()*100/len(results_smote), 6)
observed_list_smote
```

Out[121]:

```
none      25.431386
other     19.417907
work      17.303562
sleep     15.866844
shop      8.860994
school    7.239132
leisure   5.880175
Name: destination, dtype: float64
```

In [122]:

```
def plot_expected_and_observed3(input_expected, input_observed1, input_observed2, x_label, y_label, color1,
color2, legend1, legend2):
    '''Returns plots of the given lists

    Keyword arguments:
    input_expected -- list of the expected values of each category
    input_observed1 -- first list of the observed values of each category
    input_observed2 -- second list of the observed values of each category
    '''

    fig, axs = plt.subplots(figsize=(10, 5))

    chart_title = ''
    df = pd.concat([input_expected, input_observed1], axis=1)
    df = pd.concat([df, input_observed2], axis=1)

    N = len(df)
    ind = np.arange(N) # the x locations for the groups
    width = 0.25

    x = df.index

    y_expected = df.iloc[:,0]
    rects_expected = axs.bar(ind-width, y_expected, width, color='lightgreen')

    y_observed1 = df.iloc[:,1]
    rects_observed1 = axs.bar(ind, y_observed1, width, color=color1)

    y_observed2 = df.iloc[:,2]
    rects_observed2 = axs.bar(ind+width, y_observed2, width, color=color2)

    axs.set_title(chart_title)
    axs.set_ylabel(y_label, fontsize=12)
    axs.set_xlabel(x_label, fontsize=12)
    axs.set_xticks(ind)
    axs.set_xticklabels(x)
    axs.legend((rects_expected[0], rects_observed1[0], rects_observed2[0]), ('expected', legend1, legend2),
loc=1)

    def autolabel(rects, offset=0):
        for rect in rects:
            try:
                h = rect.get_height()
                if (h >= 0.1):
                    axs.text(rect.get_x() + (rect.get_width()/2) + offset, 1.00*h, '%g'%round(h,1),
                        ha='center', va='bottom')
                else:
                    axs.text(rect.get_x() + (rect.get_width()/2) + offset, 1.00*h, '%g'%round(h,3),
                        ha='center', va='bottom')
            except:
                pass

    autolabel(rects_expected, -0.05)
    autolabel(rects_observed1)
    autolabel(rects_observed2, 0.05)

plot_expected_and_observed3(expected_list, observed_list, observed_list_smote, 'activity types', 'proportion (%)', 'lightblue', 'lightsalmon',
                            'Model 1', 'Model 2')
```


b) Expected and observed frequency of chains

```
In [123]: chains_smote = pd.Series(get_actv_chains(results_smote))
          chains_smote.value_counts().head(20)
```

```
Out[123]:
home-work-none          1739
home-other-none         946
home-school-none        871
home-leisure-none       537
home-shop-none          501
home-other-sleep-other-sleep-other-sleep-other-sleep-other-sleep-none  108
home-work-sleep-work-sleep-work-sleep-work-sleep-work-sleep-work-sleep-none  108
home-other-other-other-other-other-other-other-other-other-other-other-none  105
home-school-sleep-school-sleep-school-sleep-school-sleep-school-sleep-school-sleep-none  69
home-other-sleep-other-none  63
home-shop-sleep-shop-sleep-shop-sleep-shop-sleep-shop-sleep-shop-sleep-shop-sleep-none  62
home-other-sleep-work-none   62
home-shop-work-none         60
home-work-school-none       56
home-work-sleep-work-none   55
home-other-work-none        49
home-work-other-none       48
home-none                 45
home-other-shop-none       41
home-shop-sleep-shop-none   39
dtype: int64
```

```
In [124]: len(chains_smote.unique())
```

```
Out[124]:
394
```

```
In [125]: len_chains_smote = pd.Series(get_actv_chain_legnths(results_smote))
len_chains_smote.value_counts()
```

```
Out[125]:
2      4594
13     945
3      475
4      474
6      113
5      108
1       45
8       40
7       33
10      20
9       17
11       3
12       1
dtype: int64
```

```
In [126]: plot_expected_and_observed(len_chains_test.value_counts(),
                                     len_chains_smote.value_counts(),
                                     'chain length',
                                     'counts',
                                     'Model 2',
                                     'lightsalmon',
                                     'lightsalmon',
                                     dist=0.15)
```


c) Importance of features

In [127]:

```
feature_importances = permutation_importance(ATM_dt_model_smote,
                                             X_train_ATM_smote,
                                             Y_train_ATM_smote,
                                             scoring='balanced_accuracy',
                                             n_repeats=5,
                                             random_state=123)

col1 = feature_importances.importances_mean
col2 = ATM_X_columns

df = pd.DataFrame(col1, index=col2, columns=['importance'])
df.sort_values(by='importance', ascending=False, inplace=True)
df
```

Out[127]:

	importance
age_group	0.394552
reach_bike	0.382066
ohe_origin_sleep	0.360774
education_level	0.318535
people_in_household	0.297516
reach_walk	0.282089
reach_car	0.238699
reach_transit	0.217179
has_driver_license	0.178839
is_female	0.168500
is_student	0.126554
ohe_origin_work	0.099739
is_car_available	0.099509
count_work	0.086074
count_other	0.075894
ohe_origin_other	0.071478
count_school	0.045843
count_sleep	0.040117
ohe_origin_school	0.032853
ohe_origin_shop	0.018393
count_shop	0.012090
ohe_origin_leisure	0.007423
count_leisure	0.003654

d) VALFRAM activity count validation

In [128]:

```
activ_counts_smote = activ_count_validation(results_smote)
```

In [129]:

```
chi_square_activity_counts_smote = compute_chi_square_from_values(activ_counts_test, activ_counts_smote)[0]
print('The total chi-square value for activity counts validation in the decision tree model is '
      + str(chi_square_activity_counts_smote))
```

The total chi-square value for activity counts validation in the decision tree model is 37716.733056678175

In [130]:

```
chi_square_activ_subtotals = compute_chi_square_from_values(activ_counts_test, activ_counts_smote)[1]
chi_square_activ_subtotals[0]
```

Out[130]:

```
['other',
 0    4673
 1    1465
 2     536
 3     118
 4      55
 5       9
 6       7
 7       2
 8       0
 9       2
10      1
11      0
12      0
Name: expected, dtype: int64,
 0    4657
 1    1561
 2     198
 3      63
 4      39
 5      50
 6     133
 7       4
 8       2
 9       5
10      16
11      35
12     105
Name: observed, dtype: int64,
3015.798767865106]
```

In [131]:

```
plot_chi_square_results(chi_square_activ_subtotals, 'Model 2', 'lightsalmon')
```


4.4.2 MCM module

```
In [132]: mode_counts_smote = mode_count_validation(results_smote)
```

```
In [133]: chi_square_mode_counts = compute_chi_square_from_proportions(mode_counts_test, mode_counts_smote)[0]

print('The total chi-square value for mode counts validation in this set of results is '
      + str(chi_square_mode_counts))
```

The total chi-square value for mode counts validation in this set of results is 1840.1913994258152

```
In [134]: chi_square_mode_subtotals = compute_chi_square_from_proportions(mode_counts_test, mode_counts_smote)[1]
chi_square_mode_subtotals[0]
```

```
Out[134]: ['other',
bike          73.0
car          3188.0
other_mode    123.0
pt           638.0
walk         1222.0
Name: expected, dtype: float64,
bike          68
car          3043
other_mode    222
pt           568
walk         1343
Name: observed, dtype: int64,
107.66679773669216]
```

In [135]:

```
plot_chi_square_results(chi_square_mode_subtotals, 'Model 2', 'lightsalmon')
```


5. Model 3: Random Forests

In [136]:

```
X_train_cv_ATM, X_val_ATM, Y_train_cv_ATM, Y_val_ATM = train_test_split(X_train_ATM,
                                                                    Y_train_ATM,
                                                                    test_size = 0.20,
                                                                    random_state=123)

sm = SMOTE(random_state=123)
X_train_cv_smote_ATM, Y_train_cv_smote_ATM = sm.fit_resample(X_train_cv_ATM, Y_train_cv_ATM)

X_train_cv_MCM, X_val_MCM, Y_train_cv_MCM, Y_val_MCM = train_test_split(X_train_MCM,
                                                                    Y_train_MCM,
                                                                    test_size = 0.20,
                                                                    random_state=123)

X_train_cv_smote_MCM, Y_train_cv_smote_MCM = sm.fit_resample(X_train_cv_MCM, Y_train_cv_MCM)
```

In [137]:

```
def run_cross_validation_on_forests(X, y, tree_depths, cv=5, scoring='balanced_accuracy'):

    cv_scores_list = []
    cv_scores_std = []
    cv_scores_mean = []
    accuracy_scores = []

    for depth in tree_depths:
        tree_model = RandomForestClassifier(max_depth=depth, random_state=123)
        cv_scores = cross_val_score(tree_model, X, y, cv=cv, scoring=scoring)
        cv_scores_list.append(cv_scores)
        cv_scores_mean.append(cv_scores.mean())
        cv_scores_std.append(cv_scores.std())
        accuracy_scores.append(tree_model.fit(X, y).score(X, y))

    cv_scores_mean = np.array(cv_scores_mean)
    cv_scores_std = np.array(cv_scores_std)
    accuracy_scores = np.array(accuracy_scores)

    return cv_scores_mean, cv_scores_std, accuracy_scores
```

In [138]:

```
depths_list = [5,10,15,20,25,30,35,40]

init_time = time.time()

ATM_dt_cv_scores_mean, ATM_dt_cv_scores_std, ATM_dt_accuracy_scores = run_cross_validation_on_forests(X_train_cv_smote_ATM,
                                                                                                     Y_train_cv_smote_ATM,
                                                                                                     depths_list,
                                                                                                     cv=2,
                                                                                                     scoring='balanced_accuracy')

end_time = time.time()
ellapsed_time = end_time - init_time

print('Cross-validation took ' + str(ellapsed_time) + ' seconds to run')
```



```

/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/sklearn/model_selection/_validation.py:531: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().
    estimator.fit(X_train, y_train, **fit_params)
/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/ipykernel_launcher.py:14: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().

/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/sklearn/model_selection/_validation.py:531: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().
    estimator.fit(X_train, y_train, **fit_params)
/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/sklearn/model_selection/_validation.py:531: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().
    estimator.fit(X_train, y_train, **fit_params)
/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/ipykernel_launcher.py:14: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().

/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/sklearn/model_selection/_validation.py:531: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().
    estimator.fit(X_train, y_train, **fit_params)
/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/sklearn/model_selection/_validation.py:531: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().
    estimator.fit(X_train, y_train, **fit_params)
/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/ipykernel_launcher.py:14: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().

/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/sklearn/model_selection/_validation.py:531: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().
    estimator.fit(X_train, y_train, **fit_params)
/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/sklearn/model_selection/_validation.py:531: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().
    estimator.fit(X_train, y_train, **fit_params)
/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/ipykernel_launcher.py:14: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().

```

Cross-validation took 464.6146790981293 seconds to run

In [139]:

```

# plotting accuracy
plot_cross_validation_on_trees(depths_list,
                               ATM_dt_cv_scores_mean,
                               ATM_dt_cv_scores_std,
                               ATM_dt_accuracy_scores,
                               'Balanced accuracy per decision tree depth on ATM cross-validation data',
                               'balanced-accuracy')

```


In [140]:

```
max_balanced_accuracy = np.amax(np.around(ATM_dt_cv_scores_mean,3))

optimal_depth_ATM = depths_list[np.argmax(np.around(ATM_dt_cv_scores_mean,3))]

print('The maximum balanced_accuracy score for the ATM model is '
      + str(max_balanced_accuracy)
      + ' for tree depth '
      + str(optimal_depth_ATM))
```

The maximum balanced_accuracy score for the ATM model is 0.719 for tree depth 25

In [141]:

```
ATM_rf_cv_model = RandomForestClassifier(max_depth=optimal_depth_ATM, random_state=123)
ATM_rf_cv_model.fit(X_train_cv_smote_ATM,
                    Y_train_cv_smote_ATM)

Y_pred_val_ATM = ATM_rf_cv_model.predict(X_val_ATM)

class_names = ['leisure', 'none', 'other', 'school', 'shop', 'sleep', 'work']

disp = plot_confusion_matrix(ATM_rf_cv_model, X_val_ATM, Y_val_ATM,
                             display_labels=class_names,
                             cmap=plt.cm.Blues,
                             normalize=None)

disp.ax_.set_title('ATM confusion matrix')
plt.show()

print(classification_report(Y_val_ATM, Y_pred_val_ATM, digits=3, labels=class_names))
```

/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/ipykernel_launcher.py:3: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().

This is separate from the ipykernel package so we can avoid doing imports until

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
leisure	0.055	0.072	0.062	278
none	0.717	0.762	0.739	5559
other	0.447	0.369	0.404	2493
school	0.649	0.679	0.663	1095
shop	0.162	0.190	0.175	648
sleep	0.245	0.262	0.253	1407
work	0.630	0.579	0.604	3305
accuracy			0.563	14785
macro avg	0.415	0.416	0.414	14785
weighted avg	0.565	0.563	0.563	14785

In [142]:

```
init_time = time.time()

MCM_dt_cv_scores_mean, MCM_dt_cv_scores_std, MCM_dt_accuracy_scores = run_cross_validation_on_forests(X_train_cv_smote_MCM,
                                                                                                       Y_train_cv_smote_MCM,
                                                                                                       in_cv_smote_MCM,
                                                                                                       depth,
                                                                                                       s_list,
                                                                                                       cv=2,
                                                                                                       scoring='balanced_accuracy')

end_time = time.time()
elapsed_time = end_time - init_time

print('Cross-validation took ' + str(elapsed_time) + ' seconds to run')
```



```

/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/sklearn/model_selection/_validation.py:531: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().
    estimator.fit(X_train, y_train, **fit_params)
/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/ipykernel_launcher.py:14: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().

/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/sklearn/model_selection/_validation.py:531: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().
    estimator.fit(X_train, y_train, **fit_params)
/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/sklearn/model_selection/_validation.py:531: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().
    estimator.fit(X_train, y_train, **fit_params)
/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/ipykernel_launcher.py:14: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().

/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/sklearn/model_selection/_validation.py:531: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().
    estimator.fit(X_train, y_train, **fit_params)
/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/sklearn/model_selection/_validation.py:531: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().
    estimator.fit(X_train, y_train, **fit_params)
/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/ipykernel_launcher.py:14: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().

/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/sklearn/model_selection/_validation.py:531: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().
    estimator.fit(X_train, y_train, **fit_params)
/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/sklearn/model_selection/_validation.py:531: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().
    estimator.fit(X_train, y_train, **fit_params)
/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/ipykernel_launcher.py:14: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().

```

Cross-validation took 405.35077118873596 seconds to run

In [143]:

```

# plotting accuracy
plot_cross_validation_on_trees(depths_list,
                              MCM_dt_cv_scores_mean,
                              MCM_dt_cv_scores_std,
                              MCM_dt_accuracy_scores,
                              'Balanced accuracy per decision tree depth on ATM cross-validation data',
                              'balanced-accuracy')

```


In [144]:

```

max_balanced_accuracy = np.amax(np.around(MCM_dt_cv_scores_mean,3))

optimal_depth_MCM = depths_list[np.argmax(np.around(MCM_dt_cv_scores_mean,3))]

print('The maximum balanced_accuracy score for the ATM model is '
      + str(max_balanced_accuracy)
      + ' for tree depth '
      + str(optimal_depth_MCM))

```

The maximum balanced_accuracy score for the ATM model is 0.882 for tree depth 35

In [145]:

```

MCM_rf_cv_model = RandomForestClassifier(max_depth=optimal_depth_MCM, random_state=123)
MCM_rf_cv_model.fit(X_train_cv_smote_MCM,
                    Y_train_cv_smote_MCM)

Y_pred_val_MCM = MCM_rf_cv_model.predict(X_val_MCM)

class_names = ['bike', 'car', 'other_mode', 'pt', 'walk']

disp = plot_confusion_matrix(MCM_rf_cv_model, X_val_MCM, Y_val_MCM,
                             display_labels=class_names,
                             cmap=plt.cm.Blues,
                             normalize=None)

disp.ax_.set_title('MCM confusion matrix')
plt.show()

print(classification_report(Y_val_MCM, Y_pred_val_MCM, digits=3, labels=class_names))

```

/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/ipykernel_launcher.py:3: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().

This is separate from the ipykernel package so we can avoid doing imports until

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
bike	0.628	0.646	0.637	274
car	0.872	0.869	0.871	7092
other_mode	0.573	0.540	0.556	604
pt	0.798	0.788	0.793	3526
walk	0.783	0.805	0.794	3289
accuracy			0.818	14785
macro avg	0.731	0.730	0.730	14785
weighted avg	0.818	0.818	0.818	14785

In [146]:

```
init_time = time.time()

X_train_ATM_smote, Y_train_ATM_smote = sm.fit_resample(X_train_ATM, Y_train_ATM)
ATM_rf_model_smote = RandomForestClassifier(max_depth=optimal_depth_ATM, random_state=123)
ATM_rf_model_smote.fit(X_train_ATM_smote, Y_train_ATM_smote)

X_train_MCM_smote, Y_train_MCM_smote = sm.fit_resample(X_train_MCM, Y_train_MCM)
MCM_rf_model_smote = RandomForestClassifier(max_depth=optimal_depth_MCM, random_state=123)
MCM_rf_model_smote.fit(X_train_MCM_smote, Y_train_MCM_smote)

end_time = time.time()
ellapsed_time = end_time - init_time

print('Model training for both the ATM and MCM took ' + str(ellapsed_time) + ' seconds to run')
```

```
/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/ipykernel_launcher.py:5: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y
was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using
ravel().
```

```
"""
```

```
/opt/conda/lib/python3.7/site-packages/ipykernel_launcher.py:9: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y
was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using
ravel().
```

```
if __name__ == '__main__':
```

```
Model training for both the ATM and MCM took 77.34253072738647 seconds to run
```

5.3 Model 3: Inference

In [147]:

```
init_time = time.time()

results_rf = ddas_framework(X_test, ATM_rf_model_smote, MCM_rf_model_smote)

end_time = time.time()
ellapsed_time = end_time - init_time

print('The DDAS framework with Random Forests and SMOTE took ' + str(ellapsed_time) + ' seconds to run')
```

```
The DDAS framework with Random Forests and SMOTE took 649.4449310302734 seconds to run
```

5.4 Model 3: Evaluation

5.4.1 ATM Model

a) Expected and observed distribution of trips

The first thing we will analyse on the results obtained from Model 2 is the distribution of trips

In [148]:

```
observed_list_rf = round(results_rf.destination.value_counts()*100/len(results_rf), 6)
observed_list_rf
```

Out[148]:

```
none      37.707258
work      18.979906
other     15.707697
sleep     9.465247
shop      7.016581
school    6.928736
leisure   4.194576
Name: destination, dtype: float64
```

In [149]:

```
def plot_expected_and_observed4(input_expected, input_observed1, input_observed2, input_observed3, x_label,
y_label):
    '''Returns plots of the given lists

    Keyword arguments:
    input_expected -- list of the expected values of each category
    input_observed1 -- first list of the observed values of each category
    input_observed2 -- second list of the observed values of each category
    '''

    fig, axs = plt.subplots(figsize=(16, 6))

    chart_title = ''
    df = pd.concat([input_expected, input_observed1], axis=1)
    df = pd.concat([df, input_observed2], axis=1)
    df = pd.concat([df, input_observed3], axis=1)

    N = len(df)
    ind = np.arange(N) # the x locations for the groups
    width = 0.2

    x = df.index

    y_expected = df.iloc[:,0]
    rects_expected = axs.bar(ind-width, y_expected, width, color='lightgreen')

    y_observed1 = df.iloc[:,1]
    rects_observed1 = axs.bar(ind, y_observed1, width, color='lightblue')

    y_observed2 = df.iloc[:,2]
    rects_observed2 = axs.bar(ind+width, y_observed2, width, color='lightsalmon')

    y_observed3 = df.iloc[:,3]
    rects_observed3 = axs.bar(ind+2*width, y_observed3, width, color='violet')

    axs.set_title(chart_title)
    axs.set_ylabel(y_label, fontsize=12)
    axs.set_xlabel(x_label, fontsize=12)
    axs.set_xticks(ind+width)
    axs.set_xticklabels(x)
    axs.legend((rects_expected[0], rects_observed1[0], rects_observed2[0], rects_observed3[0]),
              ('expected', 'Model 1', 'Model 2', 'Model 3'),
              loc=1)

    def autolabel(rects, offset=0):
        for rect in rects:
            try:
                h = rect.get_height()
                if (h >= 0.1):
                    axs.text(rect.get_x() + (rect.get_width()/2) + offset, 1.00*h, '%g'%round(h,1),
                             ha='center', va='bottom')
            else:
                axs.text(rect.get_x() + (rect.get_width()/2) + offset, 1.00*h, '%g'%round(h,3),
                             ha='center', va='bottom')
        except:
            pass

    autolabel(rects_expected, -0.03)
    autolabel(rects_observed1)
    autolabel(rects_observed2, 0.03)
    autolabel(rects_observed3, 0.06)
```

```
plot_expected_and_observed4(expected_list, observed_list, observed_list_smote, observed_list_rf, 'activity
types', 'proportion (%)')
```


b) Expected and observed frequency of chains

```
In [150]: chains_rf = pd.Series(get_actv_chains(results_rf))
chains_rf.value_counts().head(20)
```

```
Out[150]:
home-work-none                2531
home-school-none              1046
home-other-none                943
home-shop-none                738
home-leisure-none             456
home-other-sleep-work-none    114
home-work-sleep-work-none     106
home-other-sleep-other-none   101
home-other-sleep-other-sleep-other-sleep-other-sleep-other-sleep-none  83
home-other-sleep-other-sleep-other-none  56
home-school-sleep-school-none  47
home-leisure-sleep-work-none  31
home-other-sleep-shop-none    29
home-other-sleep-other-sleep-other-sleep-other-none  29
home-work-school-none         29
home-other-work-none          28
home-work-other-none          21
home-other-other-other-other-other-other-other-other-other-other-other-none  19
home-shop-sleep-other-none    19
home-shop-sleep-work-none     17
dtype: int64
```

```
In [151]: len(chains_rf.unique())
```

```
Out[151]:
133
```

```
In [152]: len_chains_rf = pd.Series(get_actv_chain_legnths(results_rf))
len_chains_rf.value_counts()
```

```
Out[152]:
2      5714
4      564
13     211
3      172
6      104
5       48
8       37
1        7
10       5
9        4
11       1
7        1
dtype: int64
```

```
In [153]: plot_expected_and_observed(len_chains_test.value_counts(),
                                     len_chains_rf.value_counts(),
                                     'chain length',
                                     'counts',
                                     'Model 3',
                                     'violet',
                                     dist=0.15)
```


c) Importance of features

In [154]:

```
feature_importances = permutation_importance(ATM_rf_model_smote,
                                             X_train_ATM_smote,
                                             Y_train_ATM_smote,
                                             scoring='balanced_accuracy',
                                             n_repeats=5,
                                             random_state=123)

col1 = feature_importances.importances_mean
col2 = ATM_X_columns

df = pd.DataFrame(col1, index=col2, columns=['importance'])
df.sort_values(by='importance', ascending=False, inplace=True)
df
```

Out[154]:

	importance
ohe_origin_sleep	0.285347
age_group	0.263374
people_in_household	0.214096
education_level	0.193852
reach_bike	0.148993
is_female	0.132949
is_student	0.122529
has_driver_license	0.115733
reach_car	0.112085
reach_walk	0.102298
reach_transit	0.099807
ohe_origin_work	0.089153
is_car_available	0.076224
count_work	0.070164
ohe_origin_other	0.066914
count_other	0.050011
count_school	0.036623
ohe_origin_school	0.030420
count_sleep	0.026285
ohe_origin_shop	0.017241
count_shop	0.008411
ohe_origin_leisure	0.006955
count_leisure	0.002550

d) VALFRAM activity count validation

In [155]:

```
activ_counts_rf = actv_count_validation(results_rf)
```

In [156]:

```
chi_square_activity_counts_rf = compute_chi_square_from_values(activ_counts_test, activ_counts_rf)[0]
print('The total chi-square value for activity counts validation in the decision tree model is '
      + str(chi_square_activity_counts_smote))
```

The total chi-square value for activity counts validation in the decision tree model is 37716.7330566781
75

In [157]:

```
chi_square_activ_subtotals = compute_chi_square_from_values(activ_counts_test, activ_counts_rf)[1]
chi_square_activ_subtotals[0]
```

Out[157]:

```
['other',
 0    4673
 1    1465
 2     536
 3     118
 4      55
 5       9
 6       7
 7       2
 8       0
 9       2
10      1
11      0
12      0
Name: expected, dtype: int64,
 0    5210
 1    1275
 2     152
 3      71
 4      34
 5       4
 6     86
 7       2
 8       3
 9       0
10      1
11     11
12     19
Name: observed, dtype: int64,
1303.264518669947]
```

In [158]:

```
plot_chi_square_results(chi_square_activ_subtotals, 'Model 3', 'violet')
```


5.4.2 MCM module

```
In [159]: mode_counts_rf = mode_count_validation(results_rf)
```

```
In [160]: chi_square_mode_counts = compute_chi_square_from_proportions(mode_counts_test, mode_counts_rf)[0]

print('The total chi-square value for mode counts validation in this set of results is '
      + str(chi_square_mode_counts))
```

The total chi-square value for mode counts validation in this set of results is 860.3600782319803

```
In [161]: chi_square_mode_subtotals = compute_chi_square_from_proportions(mode_counts_test, mode_counts_rf)[1]
chi_square_mode_subtotals[0]
```

```
Out[161]: ['other',
           bike          40.0
           car          1740.0
           other_mode    67.0
           pt           348.0
           walk          667.0
           Name: expected, dtype: float64,
           bike          36
           car          1677
           other_mode    66
           pt           246
           walk          836
           Name: observed, dtype: int64,
           75.0757496251874]
```

In [162]:

```
plot_chi_square_results(chi_square_mode_subtotals, 'Model 3', 'violet')
```

